

TURNkey - Towards more Earthquake-resilient Urban Societies through a Multi-sensor-based Information System enabling Earthquake Forecasting, Early Warning and Rapid Response actions

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Towards more Earthquake-resilient Urban Societies through a Multi-sensor-based Information System enabling Earthquake Forecasting, Early Warning and Rapid Response actions

TURNkey

Deliverable D7.5

Quantitative Analysis of the Social Media Communication and Dissemination and Communication Plan

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EMSC	Euro-Mediterranean Seismological Centre	France
UIce	Haskoli Islands (University of Iceland)	Iceland
EUC	Fondazione Eucentre	Italy
UStr	University of Strathclyde	UK
BUW	Bauhaus-Universität Weimar	Germany
UA	Universidad de Alicante	Spain
ARU	Anglia Ruskin University Higher Education Corporation	UK
UNIBG	Università degli Studi di Bergamo	Italy
UCL	University College London	UK
INFP	Institutul National de Cercetare si Dezvoltare pentru Fizica Pamantului	Romania
YET	YetItMoves S.r.l.	Italy
GMP	Gempa GmbH	Germany
NOA	National Observatory of Athens	Greece
NTC	Nutcracker Research Ltd.	UK
B80	Beta 80 SpA	Italy
Sim	Siminn hf.	Iceland
UPat	Panepistimio Patron (University of Patras)	Greece

GLOSSARY

Acronym	Description
TB(s)	Testbed(s)
KPIs	Key Performance Indexes
OEF	Operational Earthquake Forecasting
EEW	Earthquake Early Warning
RRE	Rapid Response to Earthquakes
FWCR	Forecasting – Early Warning – Consequence Prediction – Response
GNSS	Global Navigation Satellite System
SN	Sensor Network
SAR	Search-and-Rescue
RISE	Real-time earthquake r isk reduction for a re Silient Europe
HRB	Horizon Result Booster
METIS	Seismic Risk Assessment for Nuclear Safety
CRISIS	Comprehensive RISK Assessment of Basic Services and Transport InfraStructure

REDACT	Rapid Earthquake Damage Assessment Consortium
COSEISMIQ	COntrol SEISmicity and Manage Induced earthQuakes
FP7	7th Framework Programme
H2020	Horizon 2020
HE	Horizon Europe
DEEP	Innovation for De-Risking Enhanced Geothermal Energy Projects
PG	Project Group
EU	European
SMEs	Small and Medium enterprises
WP	Work package
UNDRR	United Nation office for Disaster Risk reduction
GP2022 Innovation Platform	7th Session of the Global Platform
EFMC2022	European Facility Management Conference 2022
CPD	Continuing Professional Development
MS	Milestone
GUI	Graphic User Interface
PAR	Participatory action research
DSSs	Development of Decision Support Systems
ETH	Eidgenössische Technische Hochschule Zürich
EASD	European Association of Structural Dynamic
RIA	Research and Innovation Action
EPOS	European Plate Observing System
SERA	Seismology and Earthquake Engineering Research Infrastructure Alliance for Europe
NERA	Network of European Research Infrastructures for Earthquake Risk Assessment and Mitigation
ARISTOTLE	All Risk Integrated System TOWards Trans-boundary hoListic Early-warning
REAR	Research for Emergency Aftershock Response
LIQUEFACT	Assessment and mitigation of liquefaction potential across Europe: a holistic approach to protect structures/infrastructure for improved resilience to earthquake-induced liquefaction disasters
SHARE	Seismic Hazard Harmonization in Europe
MARsite	New Directions in Seismic Hazard assessment through Focused Earth Observation in the Marmara Supersite
REAKT	Strategies and tools for Real Time EArthquake RiSk ReducTion
ASTARTE	Assessment, STrategy And Risk Reduction for Tsunamis in Europe
SYNER-G	Network of European Research Infrastructures for Earthquake Risk Assessment and Mitigation lifelines and infrastructures
STREST	Harmonized approach to stress tests for critical infrastructures against natural hazard
INFRARISK	Novel indicators for identifying critical INFRAstructure at RiSk from Natural Hazards
RECONASS	Reconstruction and Recovery Planning Rapid and Continuously Updated Construction Damage and Related Needs ASSEssment
ChEESE	Centre of Excellence in Solid Earth
USGS	United States Geological Survey
GNS	Institute of Geological and Nuclear Sciences Limited
EGU	European Geoscience Union
ESC	European Seismological Commission

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1 INTRODUCTION

This document provides information on the effectiveness of the dissemination and communication plan, adopted in October 2019 with the Deliverable 7.2. It also updates the Deliverable 7.3 and Deliverable 7.4, delivered only to the project consortium in May 2020 and May 2021, respectively. This is the third and last deliverable having this scope and refers to the entire length of project (May 2019-May 2022).

The TURNkey dissemination and communication plan aimed to define the project's dissemination objectives and measurable criteria for achieving them. In it we identified the main target audiences for dissemination activities and outlined the dissemination tools and channels to be used.

The overall goal of the TURNkey dissemination strategy was to widely promote the project activities and the related outcomes to the identified target groups. To this end, all consortium partners worked together to increase the visibility of the project, share key messages and receive feedback through their networks, ensuring continuity of dissemination efforts at all times.

The project applied an interdisciplinary and trans-disciplinary alliance approach with interactive engagement and communication with stakeholders in multiple areas of expertise. In each Testbed (TB), we identified and made contact with preliminary stakeholders, whose list is thoroughly reported in the section 3 of this document.

Regarding the dissemination of the project activities and results, the partners decided to use mainly the TURNkey website (which hosts a rich array of content types and the intranet) together with others channels, such as social media, open-access peer-reviewed publications, and conference presentations, reported and described more in detail in the sections 4 and 5.

The effectiveness of each channel/tool used to disseminate the project is assessed by comparing specific KPIs with target values defined in the Grant Agreement. This comparison is detailed in section 6.

Finally, the dissemination plan and timelines were always closely aligned with the deliverables and the milestones of the TURNkey project.

2 KEY ASPECTS OF THE TURNKEY PROJECT

Among all natural hazards, earthquakes lead to the highest number fatalities and, after severe storms, cause the second highest annual economic losses. In the last years, risk awareness and perception towards seismic threats have increased among the public and policy makers in many European countries. These European countries have also understood how important it is to help mitigate the seismic risks, by making the best possible use of the potential of earthquake forecasting and early warning as well as by responding rapidly after an earthquake.

To this purpose, the TURNkey project addressed the topics of OEF, also called time-dependent hazard assessment, as well as of EEW and its use, both in real-time (during an event) and in near real-time, when rapidly responding to earthquake impacts (RRE). The lead focus of TURNkey was to close the gap between theoretical systems and their practical application in Europe to improve seismic resilience before, during, and after a damaging earthquake. To do that, in the project both a FWCR platform and a cost-efficient and versatile multi-sensor unit, consisting of seismic sensors optimized for EEW and GNSS receivers, were developed.

Specifically, the TURNkey low-cost multi-sensor units integrated existing and conventional sensor networks (i.e., seismological sensor networks (SN1), strong-motion networks (SN2), structural monitoring systems (SN3) as well as the more innovative smartphone-based (SN4) and eyewitnesses' observations (SN5)) and interact with the FWCR platform. The latter works as a multi-sensor-based earthquake information system, facilitating earthquake forecasting and enabling early warning and rapid response actions (see Figure 2.1).

The main objectives of the TURNkey project were:

- to develop and test new OEF and EEW systems (within the real-time cloud-based TURNkey platform able to integrate and process data during the risk management process), supporting RRE and SAR operations, and to tangibly mitigate the impact of earthquakes on societies, buildings, and infrastructures as well as SAR teams (aftershock forecasting and early warning);
- to combine existing local/regional information and expert opinion with the elements of the previous point to provide a robust decision-making framework, and its implementation tools, which allows stakeholders to better prepare for and respond to earthquake disasters;
- to identify the potential technical as well as sociological and socioeconomic barriers (financial, human, organizational and governance) to the implementation of the TURNkey platform, to develop guidelines to address each barrier, and to conduct cost-benefit analyses of the impact of OEF, EEW, and RRE measures to be compared with conventional risk reduction measures;
- to produce training material to raise awareness amongst individuals and public/private organizations of the benefits of the TURNkey platform as well as train them in its use.

The project methodology was developed for six earthquake-prone areas in Europe (TBs), including areas affected by induced seismicity, as well as in a Worldwide site and a mobile European EEW unit for aftershocks. Its effectiveness was tested during the demonstration of the TURNkey FWCR platform, which took place at the TURNkey final meeting held in Orihuela (Alicante province, Spain) in the last week of April 2022 (see 5.2.1). The demo was attended by both local stakeholders and stakeholders from different European countries, especially from the project TBs.

Figure 2.1: Functioning of TURNkey multi-sensor units and FWCR platform.

3 IDENTIFICATION OF STAKEHOLDERS AND TARGET AUDIENCES

For the purpose of TURNkey development and the demonstration of the project results, we identified six European TBs (see Figure 3.1) as well as a Worldwide TB-7 and an additional mobile European TB-8 for aftershocks. In line with the project, the assembled TBs covered a wide variety of spatial extents, seismotectonic conditions, seismic hazard levels, and densities of population and vulnerable infrastructure. The selected TBs also had existing sensor networks and, in some cases, OEF and/or EEW systems at various levels of operation. Many stakeholders in all TURNkey TBs were contacted and agreed to contribute to the project by specifying their needs with respect to EEW, RRE, OEF, and their infrastructures. The list of the stakeholders who joined the TURNkey project in its initial stage is reported in Table 3.1. In Table 3.1, primary stakeholders are grouped by TBs and include schools, regional governments, public institutions, private companies, port and highway bridges institutions, municipalities, insurance companies, hospitals, heavy industries, civil protections, and utility companies. Figure 3.2 indicates in which distribution each stakeholder category was involved in the project actions. Citizens also played an important role in the project, especially concerning research studies carried out by UNIBG and EMSC in the framework of EEW and the communication to fight earthquake misinformation.

Figure 3.1: TBs of the TURNkey project.

Table 3.1: Stakeholders supporting TURNkey since its beginning grouped by TBs.

	<p>TB-1 Bucharest, Romania</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Municipality of Bucharest • Institute of Atomic Physics • Townhall Margurele • Gen. Inspectorate for Emergency Situations.
	<p>TB-2 Pyrenees mountain range, France</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • LFP Perthus • French Ministry of Interior • Prefecture of Pyrenees Orientales and Hautes-Pyrenees • DREAL Occitanie
	<p>TB-3 Hveragerði, South Iceland and Húsavík, North Iceland</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Municipality of Hveragerði • Municipality of Norðurþing, Húsavík • HSN Health Care Institution of North Iceland, Húsavík • The Icelandic Meteorological Office • Landsvirkjun Energy Company • OR Power • PCC Silicon • ICI Icelandic Catastrophe Insurance Company • National Commissioner of the Icelandic Police • IRCA Icelandic Road and Coastal Administration • RARIK Icelandic State Electricity Providers • Samorka, the federation of energy and utility companies in Iceland
	<p>TB-4 Patras and Aegio, Greece</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Municipality of Aegion • Arsakeia Schools of Patras • Regional Unit of Archaia • Municipalities of Patras, Kalavrita, and Dorida respectively, Port of Patras, Rio-AntiRio Bridge
	<p>TB-5 Maritime ports in Gioia Tauro, Italy</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Port Authority of Gioia Tauro • Calabria Region in Southern Italy
	<p>TB-6 Groningen Province¹², Netherlands</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Veiligheidsregio Groningen (Safety regions) • Local Waterboard for Dikes • National Waterboard (Rijkswaterstaat) • Local municipalities • NCG (National Coordinator Groningen) • PRORail • GASUnie/GASTerra • GTS (pipelines)
	<p>TB-7 Any earthquake affected area of Europe (even the world)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • General public
	<p>TB-8 Mobile EEW for aftershocks Any earthquake- affected area of Europe</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • FORMISC–SAR teams from the French Ministry of Interior (Civil Protection): chair of the INSARAG regional group “Africa/Europe/Middle East”, Security and Emergency Response Agency of the Valencian Community

Figure 3.2: Distribution of the stakeholders' categories involved in the TURNkey project.

During the second year of TURNkey, we worked to update the list of stakeholders in Table 3.1 to increase the project impact. In October 2020, together with [RISE](#), we applied to the *Service 1: Portfolio Dissemination & Exploitation Strategy - Module A* (i.e., *Identifying and creating the portfolio of R&I project results*) of Horizon Result Booster ([HRB - Service 1](#)). RISE is a project funded under the same H2020 call (H2020-SC5-2018-2) of TURNkey and similar to it in terms of addressed topics and objectives. The application got the approval and with it we gained the support of the [ICONS Foundation](#). Figure 3.3 shows the different steps of the Service1 - Module A, which started in April 2021 and lasted for thirty-five days. Participation in this service took place in collaboration with other European projects, funded under FP7, H2020, or HE (ongoing or closed), which were identified as similar to us in terms of topics and objectives. These projects were [METIS](#), [CRISIS](#), [REDACT](#), [COSEISMIQ](#), [DEEP](#); all together we formed *GeoSense – Earthquake Risk Mitigation Cluster*. The participation to the Module A of the HRB ended at the beginning of June 2021 with the *D1.1: Portfolio of Research and Innovation Project Results of GeoSense – Earthquake Risk Mitigation Cluster*. This deliverable outlined the collective results of the Project Group (PG) to be disseminated and fifty target stakeholders who could benefit from these outcomes. Those target stakeholders were grouped in the following categories:

- State, Regional, and Local authorities;
- Policy makers, Funding Agencies including EU & national digital agencies;
- SMEs and large enterprises;
- Other.

After the successful experience of the Module A, with the exception of RISE, COSEISMIQ, and DEEP, the PG agreed to apply for the *Service 1: Portfolio Dissemination & Exploitation Strategy - Module B: Helping projects from the portfolio to design and execute a portfolio dissemination plan*. As shown in Figure 3.4, this service lasted three months and, within it, ICONS supported the PG in defining and executing a joint effective dissemination plan to showcase the results. This led to the joint webinar “**GeoSense: Coordinated solutions for a more resilient society**” in May 2022, aimed to state, regional, and local authorities (e.g., civil protection) and policy makers/decision makers. The webinar was organised to present the GeoSense cluster and its results for mitigating seismic risk in Europe. The event also included a round table to discuss with the invited stakeholders the proposed solutions, their possible improvements, and applications. The webinar was promoted by each PG component through the website, social media, newsletters, and the partners' network.

Finally, we also applied to the *Service 1: Portfolio Dissemination & Exploitation Strategy - Module C: Assisting projects to improve their existing exploitation strategy*, where the goal is to improve our existing strategy towards an effective exploitation of key exploitable results. This is still an ongoing process.

Figure 3.3: Overview of the HRB Service 1: Portfolio Dissemination & Exploitation Strategy – Module A.

Figure 3.4: HRB Service 1: Portfolio Dissemination & Exploitation Strategy – Module B.

4 OVERVIEW OF THE DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION PLAN AND ITS EXECUTION

The dissemination, communication, and exploitation activities were coordinated within WP7, led by EUC. In the Deliverable 7.2, EUC outlined the project dissemination and communication plan, i.e., how the partners agreed to communicate the ongoing activities and results of TURNkey to the target audiences, the stakeholder groups of the project, and the general public. Figure 4.1 summarizes the main goals in terms of dissemination and exploitation during the whole project.

Figure 4.1: Dissemination and exploitation plan of the TURNkey project.

The objectives pursued in the framework of the TURNkey dissemination during the three years of the project were to:

- **raise awareness** about the outcomes of the project and ensure that the activities, scientific advancements, and methodologies developed within the project were widely promoted;
- **develop** the appropriate web-based tools and printed content to disseminate the project results for maximal outreach;
- **engage** all stakeholder groups in the project activities right from the onset; provide opportunities to receive input/feedback from the community; share experiences; discuss joint problems and issues;
- **promote** the project's best practices, technical and policy recommendations, and assessment tools in support of informed decision-making; ensure uptake of results and recommendations;
- **inform/educate** the audience.

To achieve the above objectives, during the project all consortium partners contributed to the dissemination efforts and to promote the adoption of the project recommendations by policy-making bodies at national and international level.

Throughout TURNkey lifetime, the dissemination of the research studies, approaches, technologies, and outcomes took place with a wide set of channels selected by partners for their effectiveness and their ability to be targetable, cost-effective, and measurable. Those channels were outlined in the Deliverable 7.2 and are:

- the project website, which hosts a rich array of content types, including the Intranet for the project partners;
- periodical e-newsletters;

- social media (i.e., Twitter, Facebook, and LinkedIn) and audiovisual material (i.e., YouTube);
- open-access peer-reviewed publications and conference presentations;
- dissemination and communication material, e.g., e-leaflets, specific press releases to newspapers, TV and radio stations;
- organisation and participation in thematic workshops, conferences, and seminars. These activities were especially addressed to the scientific community and selected stakeholders;
- project platform;
- university teaching.

During the project progress, the dissemination and exploitation plan outlined in the Deliverable 7.2 was enriched with new activities suggested by partners to maximise people awareness of the TURNkey issues and to promote the project. Most of these activities are listed in the first strategic impact plan included in the revised Deliverable 1.6. In this plan, for each identified dissemination/exploitation activity ARU indicated the target audience, the key message, the indicators of success, the indicator of progress, and the possible causes of the activity's failure. In the following, we report which of these activities were carried out during the course of the project by referring to the type of audience they were aimed at.

To engage government agencies/national organisations and/or business/critical infrastructure organisations, we had:

- Targeted presentations to key audiences demonstrating the use of the TURNkey platform in an earthquake scenario.
- A TURNkey side event at the **2021 European Forum for Disaster Risk Reduction** (<https://efdr.undrr.org/>), held in Matosinhos (Portugal) in November 2021. Unfortunately, due to a high volume of applications received, our proposal was not selected by the conference working group. However, we were offered a session as a pre-recorded event to be broadcast during the preparation day, which would have remained available and open to all conference participants throughout the entire conference. Due to the short notice with which we were informed of this possibility, the time needed to record the event, and the fact that the partners to be involved were busy with deadlines related to the project itself, the consortium agreed to decline the offer. Aware that events organised by the UN Office for Disaster Risk Reduction (UNDRR) are a good stage to showcase TURNkey and its results, in January 2022 we submitted another application to run an online exhibition on the TURNkey platform at the **7th Session of the Global Platform (GP2022)**, held at the end of May in Bali, Indonesia. Unfortunately, once again our application was rejected due to the very high number of participants. However, TURNkey participated in the GP2022 with its work on EEW, which was selected among many to be presented in the poster session of the **3rd Multi-Hazard Early Warning Conference (MHEWC-III)**. MHEWC-III was organised by the International Network for Multi-Hazard Early Warning Systems ([IN-MHEWS](#)) as a GP2022 preparatory event.
- Presentation at the **European Facility Management Conference 2022 (EFMC2022)** in June 2022. In this conference, presentations will be live streamed around Europe.

To increase the audience among the scientific/research community, we decided to apply to the *HRB – Service: Portfolio Dissemination & Exploitation Strategy*. This EU-funded service, under Modules A and B, allowed us to identify similar ongoing projects to TURNkey from any other EU, national, and regional funding initiatives and to cooperate with them (see sections 0 and 5.7).

In addition to the above, we also identified some potentially helpful actions to engage more with the general public. One of these actions involved TURNkey social media pages. In particular, we posted some single question polls on EEW and OEF, two of the main TURNkey topics, for which users had to choose an answer from among those suggested. This initiative was quite successful, especially on Twitter where there was a wider participation, even outside of our followers (see §5.10). Then, we contacted EURONEWS twice to investigate the possibility of disseminating TURNkey and its outcomes through "[Futuris](#)". "[Futuris](#)" is the

framework used by EURONEWS to disseminate the latest news about the leading scientific and technological research projects in Europe. Unfortunately, they never got back to us.

To execute the dissemination strategy successfully, WP7 always received input from all other WPs, where the majority of the scientific and technical development occurred. At the same time, during the entire progress of the project, WP7 supported the technical work and ensured that all project innovation dimensions, best practices, policy recommendations, and assessment tools were communicated to all stakeholders and end-users in a timely fashion. This two-way communication between WP7 and all other WPs in the project enabled the effective embodiment of the innovation dimensions of TURNkey into the respective scientific/technical tasks.

The deliverables and the milestones (MS) associated with the dissemination and communication strategy are reported in Table 4.1 and Table 4.2, respectively. Each of them was delivered according to its due date.

Table 4.1: Deliverables produced within the dissemination and communication framework.

Deliverable	Lead beneficiary	Type	Dissemination level	Delivery date in months
D7.1: TURNkey project web portal	EUCENTRE	Websites, patents filling, etc.	Public	4
D7.2: Dissemination and Communication Plan	EUC	Report	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)	5
D7.3: 1st Update of the Dissemination and Communication Plan and Quantitative Analysis of the Social Media Communication	EUC	Report	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)	12
D7.4: 2nd Update of the Dissemination and Communication Plan and Quantitative Analysis of the Social Media Communication	EUC	Report	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)	24

D7.5: Quantitative Analysis of the Social Media Communication and Dissemination and Communication Plan	EUC	Report	Public	36
D7.6: Report about the demonstration in Alicante	UA	Report	Public	36
D7.7: A model Business Continuity and Resilience Plan and Disaster Management Plan framework	ARU	Report	Public	36

Table 4.2: Relevant milestones for the dissemination and communication activity.

No	Milestone name	Due date in months
MS19	Project information flyer	10
MS20	FWCR Demonstration in Alicante	35
MS21	Project web-page (outreach)	6

5 DISSEMINATION TOOLS AND CHANNELS OF TURNKEY

TURNkey approaches and results have been disseminated through multiple channels. Their choice depended on the type of communication and the target audience.

5.1 TURNkey website and sharepoints

The TURNkey website served as the main tool to keep the communities and the general public up to date with the project progress as well as to provide access to the project results following their completion. It was launched in September 2019 (MS21).

Specifically, the website aimed to increase awareness about the project research and results at the broadest possible international scale. It was also used to announce upcoming events and new results, present newsletters (every ca. 4 months), and provide downloadable material. Figure 5.1 shows a part of the homepage and the main tabs of the TURNkey website, available at the domain <https://earthquake-turnkey.eu>. Additionally, the website allowed the project partners to access the area reserved for them, called *Intranet* (tab at the top right of the website in Figure 5.1), where they could share privately their project documents. The upload on the Intranet was limited to 120 MB. As consequence, EUC also made available a sharepoint provided by Google (Google Drive) to be used for larger files or for those that had to be made public. Depending on the use of the file, once a file was uploaded on Google Drive, the corresponding link was uploaded either to the Intranet or to the project website/social media accounts. Furthermore, partners involved in WP2 (*Validation and standardization of the TURNkey procedure and monitoring at the Testbeds*) used an additional sharepoint provided by UIce (leader of WP2), where only TB data were shared.

Figure 5.1: Part of the TURNkey website homepage.

As established in Deliverable 7.2, the TURNkey website was regularly updated with all the activities carried out as part of the project.

In addition, during the project the website was subject to continuous maintenance in order to make it more user friendly and clear in navigation. This has led to slight changes in the composition of the tabs and their contents over time.

To verify the TURNkey website effectiveness, the website was integrated with *Google Analytics*. Figure 5.2 reports the monthly trend of visits to the TURNkey website from the 30th of September, 2019, (date of website launch) to the end of the project. Figure 5.2 makes a comparison between *new visits*, i.e., the number of users who visited the website only once, and *total visits*, i.e., the number of users who visited the website more than once. Figure 5.2 shows that the trend for *new visits* and *total visits* remained approximatively constant over time, except for a few peaks, the most important of which occurred in February 2021. This is presumably due to the publication of three news items in the tab “News&Events” of the website, concerning: (1) the multi-sensor instrument deployment in the TURNkey TBs, (ii) an article on dynamic seismic risk communication and rapid situation assessment in the face of a destructive earthquake in Europe (Bossu et al., EMSC), and (iii) the reward to Earthquake Network app in the *AppsUP 2020* within the *Huawei HMS App Innovation Contest*. Each of these news items were also shared on our social media, thus increasing the number of visits to our website.

At the end of the project *new visits* and *total visits* were 7591 and 13181, respectively. It is worth pointing out that *total visits* is a more reliable parameter than *new visits* for monitoring the website and users’ interest in it because it is not affected by cookies.

Figure 5.2: Comparison between *new visits* (light blue) and *total visits* (dark blue) to the TURNkey website in the TURNkey lifetime.

Table 5.1 reports a comparison of the behaviour of visitors during the three years of the project in terms of: *new visits*, *total visits*, *number of sessions per user*, *page/session*, *average session duration*, and *bounce rate*. The ratio *pages/session* is the average number of pages viewed during a session. Repeated views of a single page are counted. Instead, the *bounce rate* represents the percentage of visitors who enter the website and then leave rather than continuing to view other pages within the same website.

Table 5.1 shows that visitors’ behaviour is comparable over the three years. Furthermore, as highlighted in Figure 5.2, Table 5.1 also reveals that the largest number of visitors was in the second year of the project. Nevertheless, visitors tended to stay less on the TURNkey website and to visit mainly one page per session.

Table 5.1: Comparison of TURNkey website visitors' behaviour in the three years of TURNkey.

Period	New Visits	Total Visits	Number of Sessions per User	Pages/Session	Avg. Session Duration	Bounce Rate
1 st Year of TURNkey*	1028	1961	1.91	2.46	00:02:42	58.54%
2 nd Year of TURNkey	3502	5976	1.69	1.65	00:01:09	70.80%
3 rd Year of TURNkey	3061	5244	1.70	1.91	00:01:56	57.21%

* In the first year, website data started to be tracked from the 30th of September 2019, date of the website launch.

Regarding the locations of the visits, Figure 5.3 points out that the accesses to the project website came from all over the world, but mostly from Europe (especially Southern, Western, and Northern Europe) and Northern America.

Figure 5.3: Top locations by visits to the TURNkey website from September 2019 (date of the website launch) to the end of the project.

5.2 Thematic workshops and specialized meetings

During TURNkey lifetime, monthly virtual meetings (Executive Board + WPs leaders meetings) were organized among the project coordinator (NOR) and the WP leaders to monitor the progress and to agree on plans for the various project stages. To keep track of the topics discussed, at the end of each meeting the corresponding minutes were always shared with the participants and/or uploaded to the Intranet in the dedicated area. Before the end of each WP, periodic (generally monthly) meetings were also arranged within each WP to check the respective progress and discuss on the future developments.

In addition to the technical meetings, a number of other project meetings and workshops were organised. As mentioned in section 5.2.2, some workshops were addressed only to the consortium members while others were also addressed to the stakeholders with the aim to share experiences and opinions on the project topics as well as to disseminate our activities and results to a wider audience. Due to Covid-19, most of the meetings and workshops held during the project were online.

5.2.1 Project meetings

On June 13-14, 2019, there was the kick-off meeting of the project where the representatives of all twenty-one project participant organizations took part. The meeting was organized by NOR, the project coordinator, and was held in the Scandic Holmenkollen Park in Oslo, Norway. In Figure 5.4 there are some photos of the event.

Figure 5.4: Kick-off meeting, June 2019, Oslo, Norway.

On May 20, 2020, the TURNkey consortium met online for the General Assembly 2020 (GA 2020) to share the results achieved so far and discuss any problems encountered. Specifically, the agenda of the event included: (i) the project status verification (in terms of deliverables and milestones) focusing on the 1st Reporting Period (June 2019–November 2020), (ii) a summary of the results of WP1 presented by Keith Jones (ARU) and Celia Callus (NTC), (iii) an analysis of the internal reporting that was performed at the end of the half of the 1st Reporting Period, and (iv) a status update about the impact of the COVID-19 situation (delays, contingency plan, etc.). Figure 5.5 shows a few screenshots of the GA 2020, held online through the WEBEX application.

Figure 5.5: General Assembly, May 2020.

Initially, the first annual meeting of the project consortium was planned for June 2020 in Groningen. Due to the COVID-19 outbreak, the consortium meeting was postponed and held online on September 22, 2020. The Consortium meeting was organized by NOR to prepare the important upcoming deadline of the end of the first reporting period (November 2020). The meeting was mainly focused on the algorithms to be implemented in the TURNkey FWCR platform and on the development of the platform itself. A mock-up of the GUI was also presented in an interactive way. In Figure 5.6 some screenshot on the topics discussed in the meeting are reported.

Figure 5.6: First consortium meeting, September 2020.

On February 26, 2021, TURNkey underwent its mid-term review by the European Commission. The review was held online and attended by about twenty-five people, i.e. the TURNkey WP leaders, the Project Officer and the two reviewers. The whole event lasted about six hours and resulted in a very productive discussion where all the activities carried out in the first year and a half of TURNkey were presented. Figure 5.7 shows two screenshots with people who attended the meeting.

Figure 5.7: Mid-term review meeting, February 2021.

On June 16, 2021, NOR organised the second consortium meeting. The event was mainly intended to showcase the version 2.0 of the TURNkey FWCR platform and the results of the new round of interviews with stakeholders in the TBs (PAR cycle 2). Besides TURNkey partners, members from the Scientific Advisory Board from Japan and USA attended the meeting as well as speakers from the RISE project and the [SensEQuake](#) project. The latter were invited by NOR to present the scientific work performed in their respective projects. SenseEQuake is an EU Interreg project about seismic monitoring and developing a decision support tool for end-users. The project ended in December 2020 and involved a Dutch-German consortium, consisting of companies and universities. This was a good opportunity for all three projects to share their experiences and achievements as well as to explore further possibilities for cooperation (during its three years, TURNkey collaborated with RISE on several fronts).

The meeting also included a pitch session where authors of publications shared with the audience the outcomes published so far on OEF, EEW, and RRE in no more than ninety seconds. The presentations of the pitch session are available on the TURNkey YouTube page, collected in dedicated playlists (i.e., [OEF](#), [EEW](#), [RRE](#)), and on the TURNkey website (tab “News&Events” - “Videos”). Figure 5.8 shows a few screenshots of the event that was online and attended by about sixty people.

Figure 5.8: Second consortium meeting, June 2021.

On November 19, 2021, the TURNkey consortium met online for the General Assembly 2021 (GA2021). The meeting, which lasted a few hours, mainly focused on: (i) the final set of use cases for first responders, civil protection, businesses and critical infrastructures, (ii) the demonstration tool to be used for simulation purposes with the stakeholders, and (iii) general project and administrative issues. The numbers of attendees to the event was about twenty people.

On April 25-28, 2022, the final meeting of TURNkey was held in Orihuela (province of Alicante, Spain). The event was organised by UA (a TURNkey partner) and started with the workshop "*Jornadas Internacionales de Sensibilización frente al Riesgo Sísmico*". The workshop lasted two and a half days, the first of which was aimed only at local stakeholders and included a series of presentations in Spanish, focusing mainly on (i) the seismic risk in Orihuela and its surroundings, (ii) the protection and the prevention of the built heritage in the same areas, (iii) the protocol for assessing damage to buildings following an earthquake, and (iv) the emergency management after a seismic event.

From the second day onwards (April 26), the workshop focused exclusively on TURNkey and was in English. The final results of TURNkey were shared among the partners and presented to stakeholders from several European countries. The TURNkey platform, the main product of the project, was demonstrated through the simulation of the occurrence of a damaging earthquake in the municipality of Orihuela.

The last two days of the final meeting of TURNkey were dedicated only to the TURNkey consortium. The partners took this opportunity to be informed about the last aspects related to the management and final reporting of the project as well as to discuss possible routes of exploitation and commercialisation for TURNkey and its products. During the second part of the final TURNkey meeting, the last General Assembly of the project was also held.

The number of people attending the event, both physically and virtually, ranged from around seventy (consortium+stakeholders) to forty (TURNkey consortium only). The meeting was also attended by *Alberto*

Pozza, TURNkey's EC project officer, *Fumio Yamazaki* from the National Research Institute for Earth ([NIED](#), Japan), a member of TURNkey's scientific advisory board, and *Philippe Quevauviller*, EC policy officer. The latter gave a short presentation on the Community for European Research and Innovation for Security ([CERIS](#)) and its scope and opportunities. Figure 5.9 shows some pictures of the final meeting of TURNkey while videos of the workshop organised in the first part of the event, including the TURNkey platform demonstration, are available on our YouTube channel.

Finally, Table 5.2 summarises the meetings held during the three years of TURNkey with the corresponding date and number of participants.

Figure 5.9: Final meeting of TURNkey, April 2022.

Table 5.2: Project meetings organised within TURNkey (June 2019-May 2022).

Meeting	When	Attendees
Kick-off meeting	June 13-14, 2019	21
1 st General Assembly 2020	May 20, 2020	About 30
1 st Consortium meeting	September 22, 2020	About 30
Mid-term review	February 26, 2021	About 25
2 nd Consortium meeting	June 16, 2021	About 60
2 nd General Assembly 2021	November 19, 2021	About 20
Final project meeting	April 27-28, 2022	About 70 (TURNkey consortium+stakeholders) About 40 (TURNkey consortium)

5.2.2 Thematic workshops/seminars

On January 30-31, 2020, a workshop on WP6 (*TURNkey multi-sensor unit and cloud-based FWCR platform*) was held in Oslo, Norway, to start discussing the aims and objectives of the TURNkey FWCR platform as well as its technical specifications. The event was attended by NOR, as project coordinator and WP6 leader, and the WP leaders and partners involved in the development of the tool.

Due to the start of the COVID-19 outbreak, on March 26-27, 2020, a workshop on WP3 (*Assessment of Ground motions before, during, and after an earthquake*) was held online instead of at the BRGM's offices in Paris. To maximise the time available for discussions, the presentations were pre-recorded, uploaded to the TURNkey Intranet, and watched by participants beforehand. The event resulted in a day and a half of very good discussions on OEF, EEW, and RRE that led to developing new ideas on how to achieve the project's objectives on these topics. The conveners for different sessions were UStr, UCL/EUC, BRGM, INFP, E MSC/ UNIBG, EUC, and BRGM and the overall event was chaired by UStr, the leader of WP3, with logistic support by UIce. About forty people participated in the workshop with all WP3 partners well represented. Even if the idea of a virtual workshop seemed unusual at first, we noticed that the virtual format of this workshop allowed more people to participate than a physical meeting would have. Figure 5.10 shows some screenshots of the WP3 virtual workshop.

Figure 5.10: WP3 virtual workshop, March 2020.

On the April 21-22, 2020, TURNkey's partners met together for a virtual workshop on WP4 (*Physical and Systemic Vulnerability Estimation for Rapid Loss Prediction Updating*) and WP5 (*DSSs for real-time (OEF and EEW) and near real-time (RRE) disaster prevention and risk communication*). The event was chaired by BRGM and UCL, leaders of WP4 and WP5, respectively. On April 21, the event addressed the topics of WP4 while the topics of WP5 were mostly discussed the day after. Both days, between thirty and forty-five people participated in the workshop at various times with all WP4 and WP5 partners well represented. As for the WP3 virtual workshop, the presentations were pre-recorded, uploaded to the TURNkey Intranet, and watched by participants beforehand. Figure 5.11 shows some screenshots of the WP4 and WP5 virtual workshop.

Figure 5.11: Virtual workshop on WP4 and WP5, April 2020.

On June 18-19, 2020, GMP held an online workshop to train a selected audience of about eighteen people within TURNkey in the use of SeisComp Basic, with focus on waveform data acquisition and archiving.

On July 2, 2020, as WP5 leader, UCL organized a workshop on the Task 5.3 (*Development of Decision Support System (DSS) for OEF and EEW*). The workshop was attended by about twenty participants. Some of the attendees presented their work on the development of DSSs for OEF and EEW across a wide variety of applications, including schools, ports, warehouses, and bridges. Then, the same presentations gave cue to a conclusive discussion on the implementation of DSSs within the TURNkey platform. Figure 5.12 shows a few screenshots from the event.

Figure 5.12: Workshop on Task 5.3, July 2020.

On February 9, 2021, ARU organized a thematic workshop to develop a situational analysis of the TURNkey project for the Deliverable 2.6. Its purpose was to help the consortium reflect on the project status as well as to identify potential opportunities for disseminating and exploiting the project results. Figure 5.13 shows a few screenshots of the event that was attended by about twenty people from the TURNkey consortium.

Figure 5.13: Thematic workshop on Deliverable 2.6, February 2021.

In October 2021, two workshops were organised. The first one was the final WP3 workshop, held online on October 8, 2021. This event was attended by representatives of almost all WP3 partners. There were over twenty people on the call. The event had the following two aims. Firstly, each WP3 task leader presented two slides on the main results of their tasks to remind the partners about what has been achieved. Many of these results have already been published in peer-reviewed journals or will be soon. Secondly, the WP3 leader (John Douglas) led a discussion about WP3 from a work package management point of view and what lessons could be learnt for future projects. The final section of the workshop discussed how to get the most impact from WP3 in the remaining months of the project, in terms of dissemination.

The second workshop, instead, was organised by NOR at the offices in Kjeller, Norway on October 18, 2021. The event was attended by partners involved in the development of the TURNkey platform (NOR, B80, GMP) and partners responsible for the end-user research (ARU, NTC). The meeting aimed to evaluate the performance of the TURNkey FWCR platform from the end-user's perspective at the end of the second PAR

cycle with a view to prioritizing development work during the third and final PAR cycle. To do that, simulations with the TURNkey FWCR platform were performed through hypothetical scenarios for two types of stakeholders, i.e., business and critical infrastructure organisations, and civil protection/emergency responders. A few pictures of the event are presented in Figure 5.14.

Figure 5.14: Thematic workshop in Norway attended by partners involved in the development of the TURNkey platform (NOR, B80, GMP) and partners responsible for the end-user research (ARU, NTC).

On December 10, 2021, a final joint WP4&5 workshop was held online to summarise all the activities undertaken from the beginning to the end of each WP and their outcomes. The event was facilitated by BRGM and UCL, leaders of WP4 and WP5 respectively, and was attended by around thirty people. The event was organised in the form of short presentations made by each WP task coordinators, which then led to a discussion on the success stories of each WP, as well as on related opportunities for improvement.

Beside the workshops among partners, such events were also organised to present TURNkey, its objectives, activities, and outcomes to stakeholders. In this regard, on December 17, 2019, the port authority of Gioia Tauro (TB-5) hosted a one-day event organized by EUC (TB-5 leader) to present the TURNkey project. The stakeholders of the Italian TB attended the event together with the hosting institution and the representatives of local institutional bodies, including the regional administration and civil protection. The objectives and activities in TURNkey were described through presentations and addressed in discussion groups, in which the audience actively participated. Figure 5.15 shows some photos of the event.

Figure 5.15: Workshop with the stakeholders at the port of Gioia Tauro (TB-5), December 2019, Gioia Tauro, Calabria Region, Italy.

On February 2020 Sergio Molina from the University of Alicante participated to the workshop “[*Jornada informativa sobre el Programa Anual de Protección Civil de la UE*](#)” organised by the Spanish Civil protection. The workshop aimed to provide Spanish public and private organisations with information on the requirements

for participating in civil protection projects funded by the European Community. The event was a forum to present the TURNkey project to the Spanish civil protection authorities and the scientific community.

On March 3, 2021, UCL-EPICentre organised the seminar “*A Decision-Making Methodology for Risk-Informed Earthquake Early Warning*”. In this event Dr. Gemma Cremen from UCL had a 60-minute presentation to the earthquake engineering research community on the EEW research conducted for WP3 and WP5 of the TURNkey project. The event was free and attended online by around sixty-five people, mostly from Italy and UK. The seminar was advertised on the EPICentre website and on the TURNkey website and the TURNkey social media accounts. The seminar is also available on the [YouTube channel of EPICentre](#) and added in the playlist as “Videos from Partners” in the TURNkey YouTube channel.

On March 23, 2021, TURNkey and RISE held online the joint workshop entitled “*Towards a scientific consensus to help prevent earthquake misinformation*” to fight earthquake misinformation. The workshop was mainly dedicated to scientists (seismologists, geologists, engineers, etc.) and required completion of a short questionnaire on the workshop topics before and during the event itself. The purposes of the workshop were: (i) to present the earthquake misinformation project, its methodology, and purpose, (ii) to present the survey background and methodology, (iii) to present the questionnaire results, and (iv) to assess consensus level for new assessments. The workshop was attended by about forty people while one hundred sixty people filled in the questionnaire. The TURNkey partners involved in the organization of the workshop were ARU and EMSC. A complete description of the event is available on the TURNkey website (earthquake-turnkey.eu/towards-a-scientific-consensus-to-help-prevent-earthquake-misinformation-workshop-march-23rd-2021/). Figure 5.16 shows two screenshots from the event.

Figure 5.16: Workshop “*Towards a scientific consensus to help prevent earthquake misinformation*”, March 2021.

On May 20-21, 2021, UCL and Tohoku University co-hosted the workshop: “*Developing next-generation earthquake and tsunami early warning systems for the enhancement of disaster resilience in urban societies*”. Expert speakers from the Japan Meteorological Agency (JMA), Risk Management Solutions (RMS), and University of Huddersfield took part to the event and presented on state-of-the-art early warning research activities in both regions. This was a perfect stage for UCL to present the research they carried out on EEW within TURNkey. The event was online and attended by about one hundred people belonging to the scientific community, industry, and policy makers. Before its occurrence, the workshop was advertised on the TURNkey website (earthquake-turnkey.eu/joint-ucl-tohoku-university-workshop-about-early-warning-systems/) and the social media accounts. Instead, when the event ended, the recordings were made available on the [TURNkey YouTube channel](#) and the TURNkey website (tab “News&Events” - “Videos”).

In December 2021, Benedikt Halldórsson (UIce) held a [webinar](#) on EEW and OEF in Southwest Iceland within [CRISiSLab](#) (*Crisis Response and Integrated Simulation Science Laboratory*) where he took the stock to disseminate advances made on these two topics in TURNkey. The CRISiSLab is a research and learning laboratory based in the Joint Centre for Disaster Research ([JCDR](#)), Massey University, Wellington, New Zealand.

On April 12, 2022, EMSC together with Swiss Federal Institute of Technology in Zürich (ETH, the RISE project coordinator) organised a Lunch Talk to present their [communication guide to fight misinformation](#). The guide is another result from the good synergy repeatedly demonstrated between TURNkey and the project RISE. The event was also publicised on our social media and had around twenty participants.

On May 18, 2022, as part of the GeoSense cluster (i.e., TURNkey, CRISIS, METIS, and REDACT) we held the webinar “*Coordinated solutions for a more resilient society*”. We organised the webinar as an output of our participation in the [Service 1-Module B of HRB](#). The event aimed to present the main results and solutions designed by the cluster on the topic of seismic risk mitigation to policy makers as well as state, regional and local authorities (e.g. civil protection). The webinar lasted about two and a half hours and included a round table to exchange views on the proposed solutions, their possible improvements and applications. We invited around sixty stakeholders from all over Europe and we promoted the event on our social media accounts. About thirty attendees joined the event.

Also in May 2022, Barbara Borzi (EUC), co-leader of WP7, attended the RISE annual meeting representing the entire TURNkey Consortium. At the event, the TURNkey platform and other project outcomes were presented and discussed with more than seventy participants from all over Europe.

Finally, Table 5.3 reports the summary of workshops in the three years of TURNkey, with the corresponding WP, topic, date, and attenders’ number.

Table 5.3: Workshops organised/attended within TURNkey (June 2019-May 2022).

WP	Topic	When	Attendees
WP2	Presentation of the TURNkey project to the stakeholders at the port of Gioia Tauro (TB-5), Calabria Region	December 17, 2019	About 10
WP6	TURNkey platform and its start	January 30-31, 2020	About 20 (among the consortium)
WP7	Jornada informativa sobre el Programa Anual de Protección Civil de la UE	February 26, 2020	About 70
WP3	OEF, EEW and RRE and new ideas for how to achieve the project’s objectives on these topics	March 26-27, 2020	About 40 (among the consortium)
WP4, WP5	Work packages respective topics	April 21-22, 2020	About 40 (among the consortium)
WP3	SeisComP Basic Training with Focus on Waveform Data acquisition, Archiving	June 18-19, 2020	About 18 (among the consortium)
WP5 – Task 5.3	DSSs progress in TURNkey	July 2, 2020	About 25 (among the consortium)
WP2	Situational analysis of the TURNkey project for the Deliverable 2.6	February 9, 2021	About 20 (among the consortium)

WP5	A Decision-Making Methodology for Risk-Informed Earthquake Early Warning	March 3, 2021	About 65 people
WP7	Towards a scientific consensus to help prevent earthquake misinformation	March 23, 2021	About 40 people
WP5	An event co-hosted with the Tohoku University about next-generation earthquake and tsunami early warning systems	May 20- 21, 2021	About 100 people
WP3	Final WP3 workshop	October 8, 2021	20 (among the consortium)
WP2, WP6	TURNkey platform vs end-user research	October 18, 2021	14 (among the consortium)
WP2	CRISiSLab Webinar: Thoughts on Earthquake Early Warning and Operational Forecasting in Southwest Iceland	December 1, 2021	About 25
WP4, WP5	Final joint WP4&5 workshop	December 10, 2021	About 30 (among the consortium)
WP4	Lunch Talk to present the communication guide to fight misinformation	April 12, 2022	About 20
WP7	GeoSense webinar	May 18, 2022	About 30
WP7 (representing all TURNkey Consortium)	RISE Annual Meeting	May 11-13, 2022	About 70

5.3 Conferences and symposiums

The TURNkey consortium was committed to disseminate the themes and results of the project in national and international conferences. Over the three years of the project, the partners belonging to the TURNkey consortium attended several conferences, some details of which are provided below.

The TURNkey project was presented for the first time in the **SECED 2019 Conference** (seced.org.uk/index.php/seced-2019), held in London in September 2019. NOR attended this event with a poster about TURNkey objectives, activities, and future outcomes.

EMSC participated in the **Citizen SDG conference** (www.cs-sdg-conference.berlin/en/) and **The International Training Course** organized by UNESCO/GFZ (www.gfz-potsdam.de/en/about-us/education-and-training/seismology-and-hazard-assessment/). Both events were organized online in October 2020 and saw the participation of *Remy Bossu* from EMSC, respectively to the talks:

- “OMG, Earthquake!”: Pursuing Rapid Situational Awareness for Earthquakes Globally through Citizen Seismology (with about one hundred attenders);
- Citizen Seismology: For Science & Global Risk Reduction (with about twenty attenders).

In November 2020, INFP took part in the online event **Geoscience International Symposium** (<https://geosymposium.org>) with the oral presentation entitled “*The Scientific Opportunity of a Major Earthquake in Romania*”. The latter was awarded the best presentation among all.

In the same period UA participated to the **XI International Conference of Structural Dynamics (EURODYN 2020)**, streamed live from Athens from the 23rd to the 26th of November 2020. More than one thousand abstracts were submitted to the conference, of which eight hundred and thirty were selected for presentation. Among the presented abstracts, four hundred full length papers were accepted for publication in the EASD Open Access Procedia, indexed by Scopus Database, included the two papers whose research was financed by TURNkey.

In December 2020, Remy Bossu from EMSC took part to the **1st Croatian Conference on Earthquake Engineering (1CroCEE)**. The event was entirely held online from the 22th to the 24th of March 2021. The presentation “*Rapid Public Earthquake Information: Lessons learned from the Zagreb event*” was attended by around thirty people.

From the 19th to the 30th of April 2021, the **European General Assembly 2021 (EGU2021)** gathered online. Within it, EMSC organized a joint session with the project RISE about the communication in science and earthquake misinformation. The session was entitled “*Science to Action: Communication of Science and strategies to fight misinformation - Practice, Research and Reflection*” (<https://meetingorganizer.copernicus.org/EGU21/session/40087>) and took place on April 27, 2021. Also, ARU took part to the session with *Femke Mulder*, who was one of the co-conveners of the session. The session addressed its topics through short presentations and was attended by about one hundred and fifty persons. On April 27, 2021, still in the EGU2021, there was also the session “*General Contribution on Earthquake, Earth Structures, Seismology*” where NOA took part with the presentation entitled “*The TURNkey TB4 Achaia Array: Bridging School and Citizen Seismology through Earthquake Alerting*” (<https://meetingorganizer.copernicus.org/EGU21/EGU21-14796.html>). Specifically, *Nicos Melis* from NOA presented the work carried out in the TB-4 (i.e., Patras and Aegio, Greece) within the TURNkey project. The session was attended by more than two hundred persons.

In September 2021, the **37th General Assembly of the European Seismological Commission 2021 (ESC2021)** was held online. This conference saw a large participation of our consortium, especially in Session 18 “*Towards operational forecasting of earthquakes and early warning capacity for more resilient societies*” ([ESC2021 Session 18](#)). The session was organised by TURNkey and RISE and resulted in interesting presentations addressing OEF and EEW. Talks were mainly carried out by researchers from TURNkey and RISE, although a number of researchers from outside the project also contributed to the session. More than fifty people attended each talk, thus allowing the results of the two European projects to be shared with the scientific community. Some partners also disseminated TURNkey and its activities and outcomes in Sessions 15, 16, 17, and 34. All TURNkey partner presentations were collected in a dedicated playlist and made available on the TURNkey YouTube channel.

In October 2021 UIce participated with a series of presentations in the **52nd Nordic Seismology Seminar**. The event was virtually organised by the Icelandic Meteorological Office (IMO) and brought together experts in the field of seismology and volcanology.

In April 2022, UCL participated in the call for poster presentations at the **3rd Multi-Hazard Early Warning Conference (MHEWC-III)**, May 23-24, 2022, Bali, Indonesia), which is a preparatory event of the [GP2022](#) (May 23-28, 2022, Bali, Indonesia). Their application was selected and allowed them to present and discuss their work on EEW at TURNkey in the poster session, which they attended in person in Bali on May 23 2022. Table 5.4 reports the summary of conferences carried out during TURNkey lifetime (June 2019-May 2022) with the corresponding dates, the TURNkey partners who participated, and the numbers of people who attended their presentations.

Table 5.4: Conferences attended by partners during TURNkey lifetime (June 2019-May 2022).

Conference	When	Who participated	Conference attendees
SECED 2019 Conference	September 9-10, 2019	NOR	About 50
Citizen SDG conference	October 14-15, 2020	EMSC	About 100
The International Training Course organized by UNESCO/GFZ	October 2020	EMSC	About 22
Geoscience International Symposium	November 20-21, 2020	INFP	About 80
EURODYN 2020	November 23-26, 2020	UA	About 600
1 st Croatian Conference on Earthquake Engineering	March 22-24, 2021	EMSC	About 30
European General Assembly 2021	April 19-30, 2021	1.EMSC/ARU 2.NOA	1. About 150 2. About 200
37 th General Assembly of the European Seismological Commission 2021	September 19-24, 2021	A large number of partners	About 50 per session
52 nd Nordic Seismology Seminar	October 18-21, 2021	UIce	About 40
3 rd Multi-Hazard Early Warning Conference	May 23-24, 2022	UCL	About 200

With regard to the future conferences to be held in 2022, the WP4 (*Physical and Systemic Vulnerability Estimation for Rapid Loss Prediction Updating*) and WP5 (*Decision Support Systems (DSSs) for real-time (OEF and EEW) and near real-time (RRE) disaster prevention and risk communication*) planned to have the mini-symposium entitled “*Advancing Statistical Tools for Time-Dependent Seismic Risk and Resilience Assessment: Perspectives and Challenges*” within the **13th International Conference on Structural Safety & Reliability (ICOSSAR 2021-2022)**, 20th – 24th of June 2022, Shanghai, China). As consequence, they informed and sent invitations for the event to the TURNkey partners, especially to those involved in WP4 and WP5.

Also in June, Keith Jones (ARU) will attend the **World Building Congress (WBC2022)**, June 27-30, 2022, Melbourne, Australia) organised by International Council for Research and Innovation in Building and Construction (CIB), and the **21st EuroFM Research Symposium**. At both conferences, he will showcase the research activities and respective outcomes achieved by ARU within TURNkey. While WBC2022 foresees virtual and onsite attendance options, the 21st EuroFM Research Symposium will take place in person in Netherlands in mid-June.

Partners (mainly UCL) has also shown interest in the **12th National Conference on Earthquake Engineering (12NCEE)**, hosted by the Earthquake Engineering Research Institute (EERI) in Salt Lake City (Utah) from June 27-July 1, 2022.

Last but not the least, the TURNkey consortium will participate in the **3rd European Conference on Earthquake Engineering and Seismology (3ECEES)**. The 3ECEES will be held in Bucharest from September 4-9, 2022, and will be a joint event between the 17th European Conference on Earthquake Engineering and the 38th General Assembly of the European Seismologic Commission. As part of this conference TURNkey is planning to have a booth with the projects METIS, REDACT, and CRISIS (i.e., the GeoSense Cluster). In addition, researchers from UCL and ARU/EMSC have organised together with RISE colleagues [Session 9](#) and [Session 13](#), respectively on EEW/RRE and risk communication.

5.4 Scientific publications

Towards the TURNkey end, the total number of published scientific articles was **thirty-five**, one of which in press. This number will probably increase due to papers related to the upcoming conferences (e.g., ICOSSAR 2021-2022, and 3ECEES) and further publications on scientific journals. In the following, we report the list of the papers divided per year, also available on the TURNkey website in the tab [“Outcomes”-“Publications”](#). Most of these papers are open access, except for three of them which are in green open access. In compliance with the H2020 guidelines, for these articles the authors requested the publishers to reduce the embargo period to six months, after which the publication will be made available.

2020

1. Agea-Medina, N., Kharazian, A., Molina-Palacios, S., Galiana-Merino, J.J., Soler Llorens, J.L. (2020). **Fundamental period relationship of RC-buildings in Alicante province (Spain). A first step to soil-structure resonance maps.** In: Papadarakakis, M.; Fragiadakis, M.; Papadimitriou, C. (Eds.). *EURODYN 2020. Proceedings of the XI International Conference on Structural Dynamics, Streamed from Athens, Greece, 23-26 November 2020*. Athens: Institute of Structural Analysis and Antiseismic Research, School of Civil Engineering, National Technical University of Athens (NTUA), Vol. II. ISBN 978-618-85072-1-0, pp. 4678-4686.
https://rua.ua.es/dspace/bitstream/10045/110407/1/eurodyn_2020_ebook_proceedings_vol2-4678-4686.pdf
2. Bondár, I., Steed, R., Roch, J., Bossu, R., Heinloo, A., Saul, J., Strollo, A. (2020). **Accurate locations of felt earthquakes using crowdsourced detections.** *Frontiers in Earth Science*, 8: 272.
<https://doi.org/10.3389/feart.2020.00272>
3. Bossu, R., Fallou, L., Landès, M., Roussel, F., Julien-Laferrière, S., Roch, J., Steed, R. (2020). **Rapid public information and situational awareness after the November 26, 2019, Albania earthquake: lessons learned from the LastQuake system.** *Frontiers in Earth Science*, 8.
<https://doi.org/10.3389/feart.2020.00235>
4. Fallou, L., Bossu, R., Landès, M., Roch, J., Roussel, F., Steed, R., Julien-Laferrière, S. (2020). **Citizen seismology without seismologists? Lessons learned from Mayotte leading to improved collaboration.** *Frontiers in Communication*, 5, 49. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fcomm.2020.00049>
5. Finazzi, F. (2020). **The Earthquake Network project: a platform for Earthquake Early Warning, rapid impact assessment, and search and rescue.** *Frontiers in Earth Science*, 8: 243.
<https://doi.org/10.3389/feart.2020.00243>
6. Kharazian, A., Molina-Palacios, S., Galiana-Merino, J.J., Agea-Medina, N. (2020). **Risk-targeted maps for Alicante province (Spain).** In: Papadarakakis, M.; Fragiadakis, M.; Papadimitriou, C. (Eds.). *EURODYN 2020. Proceedings of the XI International Conference on Structural Dynamics, Streamed from Athens, Greece, 23-26 November 2020*. Athens: Institute of Structural Analysis and Antiseismic Research, School of Civil Engineering, National Technical University of Athens (NTUA), Vol. II. ISBN 978-618-85072-1-0, pp. 3607-3617.
https://rua.ua.es/dspace/bitstream/10045/110406/1/eurodyn_2020_ebook_proceedings_vol2-3607-3617.pdf

7. Mihai, A., Moldovan, I.A., Toader, V.E., Radulian, M. (2020). **The geomagnetic field variations recorded in Vrancea zone during 2008-2013 and the seismic energy release.** *Romanian Reports in Physics*. <http://www.rrp.infim.ro/IP/AP512.pdf>
8. Pescaroli, G., Velazquez, O., Alcántara-Ayala, I., Galasso, C., Kostkova, P., Alexander, D. (2020). **A Likert scale-based model for benchmarking operational capacity, organizational resilience, and disaster risk reduction.** *International Journal of Disaster Risk Science*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13753-020-00276-9>
9. Toma-Danila, D., Armas, I., Tiganescu, A. (2020). **Network-risk: an open GIS toolbox for estimating the implications of transportation network damage due to natural hazards, tested for Bucharest, Romania.** *Natural Hazards and Earth System Sciences*, 20(5): 1421-1439. <https://doi.org/10.5194/nhess-20-1421-2020>
10. Tran, T. T., Ozer, E. (2020). **Automated and model-free bridge damage indicators with simultaneous multiparameter modal anomaly detection.** *Sensors*, 20(17): 4752. <https://doi.org/10.3390/s20174752>
11. Velazquez, O., Pescaroli, G., Cremen, G., Galasso, C. (2020). **A review of the technical and socio-organisational components of Earthquake Early Warning systems.** *Frontiers in Earth Science/Geohazards and Georisks*. <https://doi.org/10.3389/feart.2020.533498>

2021

12. Auclair S., Gehl P., Delatre M. (2021). **Needs and opportunities for seismic early warning prior to aftershocks for search and rescue teams: An in-depth analysis of practitioners' perceptions.** *International Journal of Disaster Risk Reduction*, 65: 102545. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijdr.2021.102545>
13. Azarbakht A., Rudman A., Douglas J. (2021). **A decision-making approach for operational earthquake forecasting.** *International Journal of Disaster Risk Reduction*, 66: 102591. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijdr.2021.102591>; <https://zenodo.org/record/5558575>
14. Bossu R., Finazzi F., Steed R., Fallou L., and Bondár I. (2021). **“Shaking in 5 Seconds!”—performance and user appreciation assessment of the earthquake network smartphone-based public Earthquake Early Warning system.** *Seismological Research Letters*. <https://doi.org/10.1785/0220210180>
15. Cremen, G., Galasso, C. (2021). **A decision-making methodology for risk-informed earthquake early warning.** *Computer-aided Civil and Infrastructure Engineering*. <https://doi.org/10.1111/mice.12670>
16. Cremen, G., Velazquez, O., Orihuela, G. B., Galasso, C. (2021). **Predicting approximate seismic responses in multistory buildings from real-time earthquake source information, for earthquake early warning applications.** *Bulletin of Earthquake Engineering*, 19(12): 4865–4885. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10518-021-01088-y>
17. Douglas, J., & Azarbakht, A. (2021). **Cost–benefit analyses to assess the potential of Operational Earthquake Forecasting prior to a mainshock in Europe.** *Natural Hazards*, 105: 293-311. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11069-020-04310-3>
18. Fayjaloun, R., Gehl, P., Auclair, S., Boulahya, F., Marthe, S.G., Roulle, A. (2021). **Integrating strong-motion recordings and Twitter data for a rapid shakemap of macroseismic intensity.** *International Journal of Disaster Risk Reduction*, 52: 101927. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijdr.2020.101927>
19. Fayjaloun, R.; Negulescu, C.; Roullé, A.; Auclair, S.; Gehl, P.; Faravelli, M. (2021) **Sensitivity of earthquake damage estimation to the input data (soil characterization maps and building**

- exposure): case study in the Luchon Valley, France.** *Geosciences*, 11(6): 249. <https://doi.org/10.3390/geosciences11060249>
20. Kharazian A., Molina S., Galiana-Merino J.J., Agea-Medina N. (2021). **Risk-targeted hazard maps for Spain.** *Bulletin of Earthquake Engineering*, 19(13): 5369–5389. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10518-021-01189-8>
 21. Kouskouna V., Ganas A., Kleanthi M., Kassaras I., Sakellariou N., Sakkas G., Papaioannou Ch., Valkaniotis S., Bozionelos G., Manousou E., Tsironi V., Karamitros I., Tavoularis N., Bossu, R. (2021). **Evaluation of macroseismic intensity, strong ground motion pattern and fault model of the 19 July 2019 Mw5.1 earthquake west of Athens.** *Journal of Seismology*, 25(3): 747-769. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10950-021-09990-3>
 22. Malekloo A., Ozer E., AlHamaydeh M., & Girolami M. (2021). **Machine learning and structural health monitoring overview with emerging technology and high-dimensional data source highlights.** *Structural Health Monitoring*, 14759217211036880. <https://doi.org/10.1177/14759217211036880>
 23. Marthe, S.G., Gehl, P., Negulescu, C., Auclair S., Fayjaloun, R. (2021). **Rapid Earthquake Response: the state-of-the art and recommendations with a focus on European systems.** *International Journal of Disaster Risk Reduction*, 52: 101958. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijdrr.2020.101958>
 24. Tubaldi, E., Ozer, E., Douglas, J., Gehl, P. (2021). **Examining the contribution of near real-time data for rapid seismic loss assessment of structures.** *Structural Health Monitoring*. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1475921721996218>
 25. Zuccolo E., Cremen G., Galasso C. (2021). **Comparing the performance of regional earthquake early warning algorithms in Europe.** *Frontiers in Earth Science/Geohazards and Georisks*, 9. <https://doi.org/10.3389/feart.2021.686272>

2022

26. Balan S.F., Apostol B.F., Tiganescu A. (2022). **The impact of TURNkey seismic monitoring network in Bucharest.** *Scientific Papers. Series E. Land Reclamation, Earth Observation & Surveying, Environmental Engineering*, 11. (in press)
27. Cremen G., Galasso C., Zuccolo E. (2022). **Investigating the potential effectiveness of earthquake early warning across Europe.** *Nature Communications* 13(1): 639. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-021-27807-2>
28. Darzi A., Bessason B., Halldorsson B., Molina S., Kharazian A., Moosapoor M. (2022). **High spatial-resolution loss estimation using dense array strong-motion near-fault records. Case study for Hveragerði and the Mw6.3 Ölfus earthquake, South Iceland.** *International Journal of Disaster Risk Reduction*, 73: 102894. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijdrr.2022.102894>
29. Fallou L., Finazzi F., Bossu R. (2022). **Efficacy and usefulness of an independent public Earthquake Early Warning system: a case study - the earthquake network initiative in Peru.** *Seismological Research Letters*, 93(2A): 827-839. <https://doi.org/10.1785/0220210233>
30. Fayaz J., Galasso C. (2022). **A deep neural network framework for real-time on-site estimation of acceleration response spectra of seismic ground motions.** *Computer-Aided Civil and Infrastructure Engineering*, 1–17. <https://doi.org/10.1111/mice.12830>
31. Galiana-Merino J.J., Molina S., Kharazian A., Toader V.E., Moldovan I.A., Gómez I. (2022). **Analysis of radon measurements in relation to daily seismic activity.** *Sensors*, 22(11): 4160. <https://doi.org/10.3390/s22114160>

32. Ozer E., Özcebe A.G., Negulescu C., Kharazian A., Borzi B., Bozzoni F., Molina S., Peloso S., Tubaldi E. (2022). **Vibration-based and near real-time seismic damage assessment adaptive to building knowledge level.** *Buildings*, 12(4): 416. <https://doi.org/10.3390/buildings12040416>
33. Ruigrok E., Rodriguez-Marek A., Edwards B., Kruiver P.P., Dost B., Bommer J. (2022). **Derivation of a near-surface damping model for the Groningen gas field.** *Geophysical Journal International*, 230(2): 776–795. <https://doi.org/10.1093/gji/ggac069>
34. Tiganescu A., Craifaleanu I.G., Aldea A., Grecu B., Vacareanu R., Toma-Danila D., Balan S.F., Dragomir C.S. (2022). **Evolution, recent progress and perspectives of the seismic monitoring of building structures in Romania.** *Frontiers in Earth Science*, 10. <https://doi.org/10.3389/feart.2022.819153>
35. Toma-Danila D., Tiganescu A., D'Ayala D., Armas I., Sun L. (2022). **Time-dependent framework for analyzing emergency intervention travel times and risk implications due to earthquakes. Bucharest case study.** *Frontiers in Earth Science*, 10. <https://doi.org/10.3389/feart.2022.834052>

5.5 E-newsletters

To disseminate the TURNkey project, its activities, and its outcomes, during its development **twelve newsletters** have been realized using *Mailchimp*, a marketing automation platform and an email marketing service:

- [Newsletter 1](#);
- [Newsletter 2](#);
- [Newsletter 3](#);
- [Newsletter 4](#);
- [Newsletter 5](#);
- [Newsletter 6](#);
- [Newsletter 7](#);
- [Newsletter 8](#);
- [Newsletter 9](#);
- [Newsletter 10](#);
- [Newsletter 11](#);
- [Newsletter 12](#).

Once delivered, we always made the newsletter available in the "News&Events" tab of the TURNkey website ([News&Events/Newsletters](#)), so that everyone could download and read it, even non-subscribers.

To reach a wider audience, the delivered newsletters were also advertised on the TURNkey social media accounts (i.e., Facebook, Twitter, and LinkedIn) and downloadable from there.

Subscribers to the TURNkey newsletter were mostly from the European scientific community and the stakeholder groups potentially interested in our activities and outcomes. Table 5.5 summarises the main data of the project dissemination through the periodical newsletters in terms of:

- **Subscribers**;
- **Opens from subscribers**, i.e., the subscribers' number who actually opened the newsletter;
- **Total of opens**, i.e., the total number of times the newsletter has been opened by all the subscribers (it considers that each subscriber can open the newsletter more than once);
- **No opens from subscribers**, i.e., the subscribers' number who actually received the newsletter but did not open it.

It's worth pointing out that *Opens from subscribers*, *Total of opens*, and *No opens from subscribers* are indices that are based on the loading of remote content into the email. If this is not enabled (e.g., by default in some email applications), the opening of the email cannot be checked (and so counted).

Table 5.6 shows the interactions of the TURNkey subscribers with the links in each newsletter, except the last one, throughout the project. This interaction was evaluated by counting the clicks on each link in the newsletters. Since these links are also related to the TURNkey website and social media, with this data we could evaluate the level of interest that the TURNkey newsletter subscribers had towards them.

Table 5.5: Data related to the project dissemination through the periodical newsletters.

Newsletter	Subscribers	Opens from subscribers	Total of opens	No opens from subscribers
<i>First Year</i>				
1	125	54	234	71
2	128	58	224	70
3	136	62	138	74
<i>Second Year</i>				
4	139	44	97	95
5	141	54	174	87
6	142	53	214	89
<i>Third Year</i>				
7	142	48	112	94
8	142	51	90	91
9	141	63	156	78
10	140	43	185	97
11	139	48	137	91
12	139	44	112	95

Table 5.6: Subscribers' interaction with the links in the TURNkey newsletter.

Newsletter	Total clicks	Clicks on TURNkey website Link	Clicks Facebook Link	Clicks Twitter Link	Clicks LinkedIn Link	Clicks YouTube Link	Other Links (e.g. publications, websites, etc.)
<i>First Year</i>							
1	20	19	1	0	0	0	0
2	8	7	0	1	0	0	0
3	23	9	4	4	2	4	0
<i>Second Year</i>							
4	11	7	2	0	1	1	0
5	29	22	0	1	0	0	6
6	29	19	1	0	0	0	9

Third Year							
7	34	11	0	0	0	0	23
8	23	9	1	0	0	6	7
9	15	9	0	1	0	4	1
10	15	11	1	1	1	1	0
11	17	8	0	1	0	0	8
12	31	17	0	0	0	2	12

Figure 5.17, Figure 5.18, Figure 5.19, and Figure 5.20 show respectively: (i) the top locations in Europe in relation to the subscribers' origin country, (ii) the top locations by opens in Europe in relation to all the delivered newsletters, (iii) the number of persons who opens each newsletter once vs subscribers' number at the time of the delivery of each newsletter, and (iv) the proportion of newsletters opened (even more than once) by subscribers' origin country. Contrary to Figure 5.20, in Figure 5.17 and Figure 5.18 we chose to not show data from the United States and Japan due to the fact that TURNkey was mainly addressed to countries belonging to the European continent. But in proportion to other countries, the subscribers to the TURNkey newsletter from United States and Japan were both equal to 1.4% while the total newsletter open rate in the United States and Japan were 4% and 5%, respectively. Finally, in Figure 5.17 the contribution of the TURNkey newsletter subscribers for whom we could not identify the origin country was equal to 3.6%. This value is instead 1% in Figure 5.18 and Figure 5.20.

Figure 5.17: Top locations in Europe in relation to the subscribers' origin country.

Figure 5.18: Top locations by opens in Europe in relation to all the delivered newsletters.

Figure 5.19: Single opens number vs subscribers' number at the time of the delivery of each newsletter.

Figure 5.20: Proportion of newsletter opened by subscribers' origin country.

5.6 University teaching

During the project, a few partners belonging to the TURNkey consortium held seminars at universities/academic institutions. In the following and in Table 5.7 we report some details of them.

In November 2020, John Douglas and Alireza Azarbakht from UStr held an online seminar on research studies carried out on OEF within TURNkey. The seminar was titled “*The potential of Operational Earthquake Forecasting for the mitigation of earthquake risk*” and was addressed to MSc students in Earthquake Engineering and Infrastructure Resilience at the University of Bristol.

In December 2020, Remy Bossu from EMSC took part in the thematic school organized within LabEx UnivEarthS ([Laboratoire d'Excellence UnivEarthS](http://www.univearths.fr/en/univearths-fall-school/school2020/)), i.e., a research program dedicated to the development of interdisciplinary projects in the fields of Earth Sciences and Physics of the Universe. The event was entitled “*Opening Science, a challenge for geosciences and astrophysics*” and took place online in three afternoon sessions from the 14th to the 16th of December 2020 (for more details: <http://www.univearths.fr/en/univearths-fall-school/school2020/>). Remy Bossu participated in the third session with a presentation titled “*LastQuake: An Application for City Seismology*”.

In March, 2022, Keith Jones from ARU included the TURNkey project in an online presentation at the Institution of Engineering and Technology ([IET](http://www.iet.org.uk/)). The presentation was part of a continuing professional development series organised by IET East Region on business continuity and disaster management planning. The presentation lasted approximately ninety minutes and was followed by an open discussion and questions. The presentation was attended by approximately one hundred people.

Table 5.7: University teaching held as part of the TURNkey project (June 2019-May 2022).

Seminars	When	Partner	Attendees
The potential of Operational Earthquake Forecasting for the mitigation of earthquake risk	November 27, 2020	UStr	About 20 people
Opening Science, a challenge for geosciences and astrophysics	December 16, 2020	EMSC	N/A
Online presentation at the Institution of Engineering and Technology	March 9, 2022	ARU	About 100 people

In addition to those teaching events that have already taken place, the dissemination of the TURNkey project results and especially the key outcome, i.e., the TURNkey platform, will be supported by the BUW within the M.Sc. Study Programme NHRE - Natural Hazards and Risks in Structural Engineering (<https://www.uni-weimar.de/nhre>). Several elements/features of the TURNkey platform are addressed in part or are closely linked to different compulsory modules (offered in consecutive semesters), like: *Seismic Monitoring*, *Earthquake Engineering*, and *Disaster Management and Mitigation Strategies*. Each of these modules is including projects which might be arranged in a step-by-step procedure for the selected target areas (home countries). Not at least, these special projects offer the opportunity to come closer to the available data of the study regions and to prepare them on an engineered (qualified) level suited for risk assessment and rapid response decision support. Currently, more than forty-five international M.Sc. students from hazard prone countries are inscribed and will get newly introduced to the platform per year. Results from the TURNkey WPs (in particular those with BUW contributions) are partially already incorporated in the ongoing lectures, taking up the state-of-the art reports. After the formal end of TURNkey, it is intended to incorporate the TURNkey platform for different sub-tasks, e.g.:

- in the course "*Seismic Monitoring*", to study OEF, EEW, and to select or develop Ground Motion Prediction Equations GMPEs - starting in the winter semester 2022/23; and
- in the course "*Disaster Management and Mitigation Strategies*", which trains special demands and procedures in situations of disasters and should enable the participants to develop appropriate mitigation measures. New and innovative training exercises are under preparation applying the TURNkey platform, although it has not yet been decided to what extent this new learning method can be implemented in practice with regard to user-friendliness and problems in preparing input data layers. However, students can run simulations to learn about the efficiency of mitigation measures and management demands from the winter semester 2022/23.

In conclusion, it is expected that the training of the platform and in form of its inherent key elements disseminate the project results to probably future decision makers and crisis managers. Thus, the academic use in course like NHRE can be considered as an essential direction of the dissemination activities because they might be ongoing after the project finalisation.

5.7 Links with international research, other EU projects and innovation activities

Throughout the project, we always focused on networking activities, forging links with other H2020 projects and EU initiatives. This networking was first of all done through some of our consortium partners. In fact, some of them were involved in numerous EU-funded and international RIA projects addressing topics in line with EEW, OEF, and RRE, such as EPOS (FP7-INFRASTRUCTURES; H2020, ongoing), SERA (H2020-INFRAIA2016), NERA (FP7-INFRASTRUCTURES), ARISTOTLE (TENDER DG-ECHO), REAR (NERC-ESRCAHRC), LIQUEFACT (H2020-DRS-2015), SHARE, MARsite, REAKT, ASTARTE, SYNERG, STREST, INFRARISK (all FP7-ENVIRONMENT), and RECONASS (FP7-SECURITY). The knowledge gained in these projects was a good basis for our activities.

Furthermore, we always kept monitoring projects on risk assessment and mitigation, for example through updated European seismic risk models from SERA as well as through exascale earthquake ground motion simulations and hazard calculations in the CHEESE project (H2020-RIA-2018).

Regarding the links with on-going EU-funded projects, it is important to underline the great synergy with the RISE project in these three years. This synergy was made possible by sharing the same topics and also some partners, who were part of both consortia, e.g., UNIBG and EMSC, who carried out significant research activities in the framework of EEW. For instance, EMSC reported their work on "*Dynamic seismic risk communication and rapid situation assessment in face a destructive earthquake in Europe*" as a newsletter item in the TURNkey and RISE project.

During the second year of TURNkey, EMSC also set up a joint RISE-TURNkey working group aiming at well communicating in science and fighting misinformation. The group is led by EMSC and involves also

researchers from ARU as well as partners from other institutions, such as USGS and GNS Science. All the activities carried out by this working group resulted in:

- the workshop “Towards a scientific consensus to help prevent earthquake misinformation”, the details of which are presented in section 5.2.2;
- the joint session TURNkey-RISE, titled “Science to Action: Communication of Science and strategies to fight misinformation - Practice, Research and Reflection” within the [EGU2021](#) (27th of April 2021, meetingorganizer.copernicus.org/EGU21/session/40087), the details of which are presented in section 5.3;
- the joint session TURNkey-RISE, titled “Seismology, geoethics and society: risk communication at the service of risk reduction” within the [3ECEES](#) (3ceees.ro/wp-content/uploads/2022/02/S13_Seismology%5eJ-geoethics-and-society-risk-communication.pdf);
- a communication guide to fight misinformation, published in February 2022. The guide is available at the ETH (RISE Project Coordinator) online repository (research-collection.ethz.ch/handle/20.500.11850/530319). As reported in the section 5.2.2, on April EMSC and ETH (the RISE project coordinator) organized an online Lunch Talk to present the guide.

As already mentioned in the section 5.2.1, we also invited RISE and SenseEQuake projects to join the 2nd TURNkey annual consortium meeting (June 16, 2021). Both projects accepted our invitation and agreed to present their activities and outcomes in the event. Simultaneously, we exchanged with them what we did to that stage of the project. This was a good chance for us to investigate further opportunities for cooperation. With the same aim, TURNkey took part to the RISE online mid-term conference (May 26-28, 2021) and the RISE annual meeting held in Florence in May 11-13, 2022.

TURNkey and RISE had also a joint session within the 37th General Assembly of the European Seismological Commission ([ESC2021](#)), scheduled for September 2021. More details are available in the section 5.3. Another collaboration with RISE will be the Session 9, titled “From earthquake early warning to rapid response – integrating state-of-the-art from real-time seismology and earthquake engineering”, within the [3ECEES](#) (3ceees.ro/wp-content/uploads/2022/02/S09_From-Earthquake-Early-Warning-to-Rapid-Response.pdf). This session will focus on EEW and RRE and has been organised by UCL (our partner) together with other researchers who have an accredited expertise in EEW, including some working in the RISE project.

As already reported in section 0, TURNkey and RISE worked also together within the Service 1 - Module A (i.e., *Identifying and creating the portfolio of R&I project results*) of HRB. This service led us to collaborate with six other EU-funded projects in the Module A of HRB, thus creating the GeoSense cluster. The details of these projects are given in the Table 5.8. Of these projects, only three then decided to apply together with TURNkey to the Module B of the HRB, the final result of which was the joint webinar “**GeoSense: Coordinated solutions for a more resilient society**” in May 18, 2022 (see section 5.2.2).

Table 5.8: EU-funded projects with which TURNkey and RISE collaborated within the Service 1- Module A of HRB.

Acronym	Description and Funding Programm	Period
METIS	Seismic risk assessment for nuclear safety	Ongoing (2020 – 2024)
CRISIS	Comprehensive RISK assessment of basic services and transport InfraStructure	Ongoing (2020 - 2022)
REDACt	Rapid Earthquake Damage Assessment Consortium	Ongoing (2020 –2022)
COSEISMIQ	COntrol SEISmicity and Manage Induced earthQuakes	Ongoing (2018-2021)
DEEP	Innovation for De-Risking Enhanced Geothermal Energy Projects	Ongoing (2020-2023)

In addition to the above, it is important to mention the support that TURNkey had from the experts of worldwide institutions (with a strong focus on USA, Japan, Taiwan, and New Zealand) that are leaders in their fields, i.e.:

- *Mitsuyuki Hoshiba*, Japan Meteorological Agency (JMA);
- *Fumio Yamazaki*, National Research Institute for Earth Science and Disaster Resilience (NIED);
- *Paul Earle*, United States Geological Survey (USGS);
- *Qingkai Kong*, University of California, Berkeley (UCB).

They served on the Scientific Advisory Board (SAB) and provided their guidance and expertise during the course of the entire project. However, we also increased the number of these experts inviting Josh Bashoum, the head of Early Warning Labs in USA, to join the second TURNkey annual consortium meeting (June 16, 2021). In spite of the time difference, he attended our meeting until the end and shared with us his experience on EEW, positively evaluating what was done on the topic within TURNkey.

Finally, TURNkey's TB-3 (Hveragerði, South Iceland and Húsavík, North Iceland) and TB-4 (Patras and Aegio, Greece) are co-located within Permanent Supersites of the GEO Geohazard Supersites and Natural Laboratory (GSNL) initiative and contributed to a better understanding and mitigation of geohazard in these areas. The GEO-GSNL is a voluntary international partnership aiming to improve, through an Open Science approach, geophysical scientific research and geohazard assessment in support of Disaster Risk Reduction. GEO-GSNL is compliant with the new GEO Strategic Plan, and with the role of science as envisioned in the Sendai Framework for Disaster Risk Reduction 2015-2030.

5.8 Project flyers

As stated in the Grant Agreement, in March 2020 the project flyer (corresponding to MS19) was delivered to all TURNkey newsletter subscribers.

The project flyer was made in electronic format and described in an effective way the TURNkey project and its objectives. Nevertheless, it could also be used in paper format to be distributed at events, such as conferences and meetings/workshop with stakeholders, as done in the final meeting of TURNkey. The TURNkey flyer is available at this link:

- <https://earthquake-turnkey.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/03/The-TURNkey-Flyer.pdf>,

on the page "The project", sub-tab of the tab "About", in the project website.

For a greater diffusion, the same link was posted on TURNkey social media accounts, to make the flyer downloadable even for those who didn't subscribe to the TURNkey newsletter at the time of delivery.

Afterwards, the project flyer was also made available at the sub-tab "Leaflets" in "Outcomes", which also collects the leaflets produced by UA as project promotional material to be distributed during the final TURNkey event. These flyers are about the TURNkey platform and about the topics of, OEF, EEW, and RRE and are available in both in English and Spanish.

5.9 Press releases and media

Press releases announce and disseminate the project results to the media, online scientific journals, news agencies, trade magazines, and press stakeholders to ensure a high impact and wide distribution of the project output.

During the first year of the project, press releases about TURNkey were published in a series of Norwegian newspapers, mostly after the project kick-off meeting. Similar press releases were also published in Spain both in the section "Actualidad Universitaria" of the University of Alicante and the newspaper "Información".

To reach a wider audience (e.g., public, decision makers and policy makers) and not only the scientific community, these press releases are in native language. Three of them are not available anymore while the others can be read at the following links:

- <https://kommunikasjon.ntb.no/pressemelding/norge-far-sentral-rolle-i-forskningsprosjekt-om-jordskjelvvarsling?publisherId=16087784&releaseId=17866233> (in Norwegian);
- <http://www.bygg.no/article/1397563> (in Norwegian);
- <https://www.nrk.no/nyheter/norsar-skal-lede-jordskjelvprosjekt-1.14586224> (in Norwegian);
- <https://web.ua.es/es/actualidad-universitaria/2019/julio19/15-21/la-ua-participa-en-el-desarrollo-de-un-sistema-de-informacion-sismica-que-permitira-gestionar-emergencias-en-tiempo-real.html> (in Spanish);
- <https://www.diarioinformacion.com/alicante/2019/07/17/ua-participa-desarrollo-sistema-informacion/2169698.html> (in Spanish).

After the M6.4 Albania earthquake on November 26, 2019, Volker Oye (Head of Department Applied Seismology at NORSAR) was invited to NRK Radio to give information on earthquakes. In the interview, she also presented the TURNkey project in Norwegian (<https://radio.nrk.no/serie/nyhetslunsj/NPUB33023519/26-11-2019>).

During the second year of the project, NOR released two press releases in Norwegian about the intense seismic activity recorded by the TURNkey sensors in Iceland. This seismic activity led to a volcanic eruption in the valley of Geldingadalir on the 19th of March 2021. Unfortunately, only one of these press releases is available and can be read at the following link:

- [Omfattende seismisk aktivitet på Island - NORSAR](#).

More press releases were also released in the third year of TURNkey, starting from June 2021 when Temblor published an article about earthquake risk reduction activities in Europe featuring TURNkey and our researcher Femke Mulder from ARU.

Several press releases about the app Earthquake Network by Francesco Finazzi and EEW (UNIBG, a TURNkey partner) were also published at the end of September/beginning of October 2021. These press releases, two of which are not available anymore in the journal website, are in Italian and some of them were published several times on different magazines. Although TURNkey was not directly mentioned in some press releases, they are nevertheless linked to it. In fact, some research activities on EEW that are behind the app were carried out in the TURNkey project. For its research on EEW, TURNkey was also mentioned in the report "[Investment in Disaster Risk Management in Europe Makes Economic Sense](#)" produced by World Bank staff with external contributions.

Besides the above, in September 2021 both [Horizon Magazine](#) and [EU Research Magazine](#) contacted us to write an article about TURNkey project, activities, and outcomes. We agreed with it and this resulted in two press releases titled [Keeping one step ahead of earthquakes](#) and [New system for effective earthquake response](#) (pag. 25), respectively. Additionally, the contract signed with the EU Research Magazine allowed us to have their support on the project dissemination through their social media pages. This was a great opportunity of dissemination for TURNkey since they have more than thirty-five thousand all over the world.

A few press releases were also published on the activities carried out on EEW by UCL and EUC within the TURNkey project. Two of these press releases are in Italian.

With the exception of the articles published in Horizon Magazine and EU Research Magazine, all the press releases of the third year of TURNkey are available at the following links, including the one in Spanish announcing the final TURNkey meeting in Orihuela (Alicante province, Spain).

- [European companies get help prepping for the next earthquake](#) (in English)
- [Un'app per smartphone segnala l'arrivo di un terremoto](#) (in Italian)
- [Un'app per smartphone segnala l'arrivo di un terremoto](#) (in Italian)
- [Un'app per smartphone segnala l'arrivo di un terremoto](#) (in Italian)

- [Forti terremoti, con lo smartphone per avvisare la popolazione: lo studio parte da Bergamo](#) (in Italian)
- [Bergamo, così lo smartphone salva dai terremoti. La ricerca del professore dell'Università](#) (in Italian)
- [Forti terremoti, gli smartphone possono preallertare: lo studio di un docente dell'Unibg](#) (in Italian)
- [Smartphone possono preallertare la popolazione in caso di sisma](#) (in Italian)
- [Dimostrata l'efficacia del rilevamento in tempo reale di terremoti tramite reti smartphone](#) (in Italian)
- [Dimostrata l'efficacia del rilevamento in tempo reale di terremoti tramite reti smartphone](#) (in Italian)
- [Dimostrata l'efficacia del rilevamento in tempo reale di terremoti tramite reti smartphone](#) (in Italian)
- [Dimostrata l'efficacia del rilevamento in tempo reale di terremoti tramite reti smartphone](#) (in Italian. The translation is also available in different languages)
- [L'App per smartphone in grado di prevedere il terremoto](#) (in Italian)
- [Terremoti, arriva l'app per l'allerta in tempo reale](#) (in Italian)
- [Earthquake Network, l'app per l'allerta terremoti in tempo reale](#) (in Italian)
- [Earthquake Network, l'app per l'allerta terremoti in tempo reale](#) (in Italian)
- [Earthquake network, l'app che segnala l'arrivo di un terremoto](#) (in Italian)
- [Earthquake early warning system could save lives in southern Europe](#) (In English)
- [Terremoti: verso un sistema di early warning in Italia?](#) (In Italian)
- [Pubblicato su Nature Communication l'articolo "Investigating the potential effectiveness of earthquake early warning across Europe" di Cremen, G., Galasso, C. & Zuccolo, E.](#) (In Italian)
- [web.ua.es/es/actualidad-universitaria/2022/abril2022/11-13/orihuela-acoge-las-iii-jornadas-internacionales-de-sensibilizacion-frente-al-riesgo-sismico-en-la-provincia-de-alicante.html](#) (in Spanish).

Lastly, the final TURNkey meeting was advertised via radio through an interview featuring Sergio Molina from UA (a TURNkey partner and the event organiser) who presented the project and the issues addressed within it. The interview was in Spanish and is available at this following link: cadenaser.com/2022/04/23/sergio-molina-la-alerta-temprana-permitiria-enviar-avisos-a-las-ciudades-antes-de-la-llegada-de-las-ondas-sismicas/.

5.10 Social media

To further disseminate the results of the project to a broader audience, in October 2019 we created TURNkey accounts on, [Facebook](#), [LinkedIn](#), and [Twitter](#). With the social media people can actively participate in the project and give their opinions and discuss. Additionally, to provide project results in a clear, direct, and visual way, we also created a [YouTube](#) channel of TURNkey. The social media pages of TURNkey were regularly updated with the latest news from the project activities and, to reach a wider audience, the posts were often shared by our partners on their social media accounts. In particular, as leader of the subtask 7.1.2, EMSC contributed to disseminate TURNkey activities through its social media accounts, especially on Twitter where its page ([@LastQuake](#)) is very popular. In particular, in here EMSC has actively interacted with the TURNkey Twitter page ([@EuTurnkey](#)), by adding likes and retweeting its posts. On average, these posts reached about ten likes and retweets each.

In order to easily recall, group, and/or visualise what concerns OEF, EEW and RRE, our posts were usually accompanied by the following hashtags:

- **#EEW and #EEWS;**
- **#OEF;**
- **#earthquake #response.**

Generally, the above hashtags were also accompanied by other hashtags that vary depending on the posts. We also often used the hashtag **#H2020** to recall the program within which TURNkey was funded.

Below we report some data on the number of people who followed TURNkey since the opening of the project social media accounts (October 2019) to its conclusion, making a distinction between its three years. The

effectiveness of the TURNkey social communication activity has been measured through a series of performance indicators available in the social media themselves. Specifically, for each social media we report the minimum, maximum, and median values of these performance indicators, obtained considering all the posts published during the three years of the project. These performance indicators are:

- **Impressions** indicate the number of times that a TURNkey content is displayed, no matter if it was clicked or not;
- **Reactions** define the response of the audience on a TURNkey post (e.g., like, love, etc.);
- **Shares** define the number of times a post is shared on the LinkedIn and Facebook accounts of other people. In Twitter it is better known as **Retweets**;
- **Clicks** define the number of clicks on a post, including the click on a link, a media, a picture, a hashtag, etc.;
- **Engagement** indicates the action that people take on posts and is given by the sum of reactions, shares, and clicks;
- **Engagement rate** is a metric that tracks how involved the audience is with a TURNkey content. In LinkedIn, Twitter and YouTube, the engagement rate is calculated as the number of engagements divided by the number of impressions. Instead, in Facebook it is calculated as the number of engaged users divided by post reach (unique). Engaged users is the number of people who clicked anywhere in posts while post reach (unique) is the number of people who saw a post. These two variables are available in the Facebook Graph API.

5.10.1 Facebook

Upon delivery of this document, on Facebook the TURNkey page had reached **131** followers, **125** likes (even from not followers), and **74** posts. The latter were mostly about project activities, such as the delivery of a newsletter and the occurrence of a workshop. The effectiveness of the published posts was evaluated by using the tool *Insights* provided by Facebook. Table 5.9 compares the number of the total followers, the total posts, and the performance indicators that TURNkey had on Facebook throughout its lifetime. The performance indicators are calculated on the basis of the total number of posts published in the three years of the project. If we analyse the performance indicators, in the second year their median and maximum values are higher than those referring to the first and the third year, except for *engagement rate*, while the minimum values are comparable.

The fact that in the first and the third year the engagement rate has respectively the maximum value and the median and maximum values higher than those referred to the second year is the result of the low interaction people had with our content. Since there were not many clicks and/or shares of our content in those periods, and especially in the last year of TURNkey, the number of people reached through our posts on Facebook might have been lower than in the second year of the project.

In addition to what is reported in the Table 5.9, it is important to underline that during the whole project, the posts allowed us to reach a number of people (i.e., *People reached*) ranging from a minimum of about **5 persons**, of whom 2 were *fans* and 3 were *non-fans*, to a maximum of **1639 persons**, of whom 67 were *fans* and 1572 were *non-fans*. *People reached* indicate how many people saw either a specific post or any content posted by a Facebook page while *Fans* are all persons who like our page.

Table 5.9: Statistics for TURNkey posts on Facebook for the whole project lifeline.

	October 2019-April 2020	May 2020-April 2021	May 2021-Project End
Total number of followers	107	125	131
Total number of posts	10	32	74

Performance indicators; median (minimum, maximum)			
Impressions	22.5 (11, 1248)	93.5 (31, 2008)	52 (21, 410)
Reactions	4.5 (2, 9)	5 (1, 24)	3 (0, 12)
Shares	1 (0, 3)	1 (0, 4)	0 (0, 2)
Clicks	1 (0, 38)	5 (0, 75)	4 (0, 31)
Engagement	7 (2, 49)	10.5 (1, 97)	6.5 (0, 39)
Engagement rate	7% (0%, 40%)	11% (2%, 22%)	12% (0%, 57%)

The tool *Insights* also allowed to statistically evaluate the demographics and the sources of our audience (e.g., age, gender, and location), as shown in Figure 5.21 which reports an estimation of people following the TURNkey page on Facebook. The data is expressed in percentage and the audience is grouped by geographic areas, age, and gender. Figure 5.21 highlights that the people who have shown the greatest interest in the project are European, male, and between 25 and 54 years of age. Among the European, most of the followers are from Italy. Finally, Figure 5.22 indicates respectively the number of times that the TURNkey page has been viewed in the three year of the project. Except for a peak of 83 views in the second year, when the post on the sensors' deployment at the port of Gioia Tauro was published (January 2021), our page had a quite low number of visits per month. As Figure 5.23 shows, all the views mainly interested the section "Home" where all our posts are available.

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure 5.21: Proportion of people following TURNkey on Facebook grouped by (a) Europe and Rest of the world, (b) European countries, and (c) gender and age, from the launch of the Facebook account to the end of project.

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure 5.22: The number of times that the TURNkey profile has been viewed in (a) the first year, (b) the second year, and (c) the third year of the project.

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure 5.23: The number of views to each page profile tab in (a) the first year, (b) the second year, and (c) the third year of the project.

5.10.2 LinkedIn

Upon delivery of this document, on LinkedIn the TURNkey page had reached **215** followers and **89** posts, most of which were about project activities, such as the delivery of a newsletter and the occurrence of a workshop. The effectiveness of the published posts was evaluated by using the tool *Insights* provided by LinkedIn. In particular, Table 5.10 compares the number of the total followers, the total posts, and the performance indicators that TURNkey had on LinkedIn throughout its lifetime. The performance indicators are calculated on the basis of the total number of posts published in each of the three years of the project. If we analyse the performance indicators in Table 5.10, in the first year of the project the median values are higher than those in the following two years, except for impressions whose median value is slightly lower than that of the second year. This shows that people interacted with the content posted on our profile in a greater and more homogeneous way in the first year rather than in the following ones. In the second and third years, in fact, people only showed interest in specific posts, such as the one about the final WP4&WP5 workshop, for which there were 1855 *impressions*, 94 *clicks*, 24 *likes*, and 2 *shares*. This behaviour also explains why the minimum values are equal to zero for some performance indicators.

Since we had already noticed this trend at the end of the second reporting period, in the last year of the project we tried to increase the interaction of people with our page in LinkedIn by publishing a series of polls provided by some of our partners. Although they were open to the public, i.e. even those who did not follow our LinkedIn page, only some TURNkey followers interacted with them. This also explains why there was not the same participation as for the same polls published instead on Twitter (see 5.10.3). Figure 5.24 shows one of the posted polls.

Table 5.10: Statistics for TURNkey posts on LinkedIn for the whole project lifetime.

	October 2019-April 2020	May 2020-April 2021	May 2021-Project End
Total number of followers	77	140	215
Total number of posts	10	35	89
Performance indicators; median (minimum, maximum)			
Impressions	339 (118, 1382)	353 (133, 1051)	302 (35, 2115)
Reactions	10.5 (3, 19)	10 (0, 35)	7 (0, 56)

Shares	4.5 (1, 8)	1 (0, 7)	1 (0, 5)
Clicks	30.5 (3, 289)	15 (4, 90)	13 (1, 638)
Engagement	44.5 (7, 314)	18 (5, 128)	24 (1, 700)
Engagement rate	12.58% (4.03%, 22.72%)	7.37% (2.69%, 17.48%)	6.84% (0.95%, 33.10%)

Figure 5.24: One of the polls published on the TURNkey page on LinkedIn.

The tool *Analytics* also allows to statistically evaluate the demographics and the sources of our audience (e.g., location and job) in LinkedIn. Specifically, Figure 5.25 reports an estimation of the followers that the TURNkey page had on LinkedIn toward the end of the project, grouped by geographic area and job function. Figure 5.25 confirms the trend noticed in the previous years, i.e., the people who have shown the greatest interest in the project are European, mostly from Italy, Norway, United Kingdom, and France, and mainly belong to the fields of engineering, education, and research. Figure 5.26 reports, instead, the trend of total views that TURNkey account had on LinkedIn from its launch to the its end. In total the TURNkey page was visited around 2450 times, i.e., about 600, 840, and more than 1000 times during the first, the second, and the third year of the project, respectively. In Figure 5.26 the graph shows that the number of visits dropped down after April 2020 but then increased in the following months with a peak in March 2021. The reason of this peak is presumably related to the interest aroused by the posts published on the intense seismic activity recorded in Iceland, monitored by TURNkey sensors deployed on the territory. After this peak, the number of visits again decreased and reached its minimum value in August 2021 to then re-increase at times in the following months. Finally, the graph of Figure 5.26 confirms what was found in the analysis of the performance indicators of the posts defined at the beginning of the section, i.e. people showed a greater and more constant interest in our LinkedIn page in the first year of the project. Then, this interest became lower and highly variable over time.

(c)

Figure 5.25: Proportion of people following TURNkey on LinkedIn grouped by (a) Europe and Rest of the world, (b) European countries, and (c) Job function at the end of the project.

Figure 5.26: Total page views from the launch of the TURNkey LinkedIn account to the end of the project.

5.10.3 Twitter

Upon delivery of this document, on twitter the TURNkey page had reached **234** followers and **89** tweets, most of which were about project activities, such as the delivery of a newsletter and the occurrence of a workshop. The effectiveness of each published tweets was evaluated by using the tool *Insights* provided by Twitter. In particular, Table 5.11 compares the number of the total followers, the total tweets, and the performance indicators that TURNkey had on Twitter throughout its lifetime. The performance indicators are calculated on the basis of the total number of tweets published in each of the three year of the project. If we compare the number of tweets posted per year, it's evident that we increased our activity on Twitter over time. This resulted in an increase in the number of people who followed our page and/or saw and interacted with our contents. This is also proved by the high values of *impressions* (minimum, median, and maximum) in Table 5.11, which refer not only to our followers but also to a large number of people outside of them. These people were reached mainly through the sharing of our posts by our partners and the use of hashtags. The latter, in fact, allow to group posts by content and have them appear on the wall of all those who search for a specific content. To increase the interaction of users with our tweets and to better disseminate TURNkey, its activities, and results, we also posted a series of polls on Twitter. An example is shown in the Figure 5.27. As already mentioned in the section 5.10.2, the same poll was also published on LinkedIn, but with less success. As shown in Figure 5.24 e Figure 5.27, for the same post we recorded 9 and 101 votes in LinkedIn and Twitter, respectively.

On the basis of the above and by comparing the values of the performance indicators reported in Table 5.9, Table 5.10, and Table 5.11 for each social media, we can conclude that Twitter is certainly the social media that allowed the dissemination of our content to a wider and more general audience.

Table 5.11: Statistics for TURNkey tweets for the whole project lifetime.

	October 2019-April 2020	May 2020-April 2021	May 2021-Project End
Total number of followers	20	186	234
Total number of tweets	10	33	89
Performance indicators; median (minimum, maximum)			
Impressions	861 (560, 3189)	3023 (501, 28908)	881.5 (24, 20837)
Reactions	3 (0, 10)	6 (1, 27)	4 (0, 85)
Retweets	1 (0, 4)	2 (0, 10)	2 (0,131)
Clicks	11 (4, 72)	30 (0, 252)	14 (2, 593)
Engagement	15.5 (5, 86)	37.5 (1, 291)	19 (2, 829)
Engagement rate	1.62% (0.89%, 3.51%)	1.62% (0.2%, 6.3%)	1.85% (0.28%, 20.83%)

Figure 5.27: One of the polls published on the TURNkey page on Twitter.

5.10.4 YouTube

Upon delivery of this document, the TURNkey YouTube channel had **32** followers and hosted **43** videos, uploaded individually or in playlists (e.g., ECS 2021 videos). These videos included two videos made by UCL and BRGM, uploaded on their respective YouTube channel. The latter were collected in the playlist under "*Videos from partners*".

Videos from the workshop with the stakeholders, held during the TURNkey final meeting in Orihuela (see section 5.2.1), are also planned to be collected in a dedicated playlist. In this way all the presentations made by our partners and the demo of the TURNkey platform will be available to everyone, but especially to those partners and stakeholders who could not attend the event, even remotely.

We also plan to upload the final video of TURNkey produced by [Scienseed](#) on our YouTube channel. This video, not available at the moment, aims to highlight what were the objectives, activities, and results achieved within the project through a series of interviews made with some of the TURNkey consortium partners.

Most of the videos in our YouTube channel were posted on the TURNkey website and social media pages. This allowed us to reach a wider audience and thus increase their impact and dissemination.

To evaluate the users' interaction with the TURNkey channel and contents, we used *YouTube Analytics*. We cannot use the same tool for videos in the "*Videos from partners*" playlist, since they are uploaded to partners' YouTube channels. For those, in fact, we could only analyse users' interactions through the numbers of views, which were 234 and 193, respectively for the videos by UCL and BRGM.

With regard to the videos uploaded on the TURNkey channel, Table 5.12 compares the number of the total subscribers, the total videos, and the performance indicators that TURNkey had on its YouTube channel throughout its lifetime. The performance indicators reported in Table 5.12 are calculated on the basis of the total number of videos published in each of the three years of the project.

Table 5.12 shows that we started to upload first videos in the second year of the project, which is when we started to get the first project results. In particular, in the second year, we:

- disseminate the video on the shaking table tests of low-cost seismic instrumentation at the University of Strathclyde; and

- shared the (ii) the recorded video from the EPICentre-UCL YouTube channel about the seminar “A Decision-Making Methodology for Risk-Informed Earthquake Early Warning”, held online by Gemma Cremen.

Since it is not possible to track data on videos posted on YouTube pages other than the TURNkey one, for the second year Table 5.12 shows the performance indicators referring only to the video produced by UStr, without the minimum and maximum values. This data cannot therefore be compared with those of the third year, which are derived from the analysis of tracking data referring to many more videos posted on our YouTube page.

As highlighted by the data shown in Table 5.12, we increased our activity on our YouTube channel from the beginning of the third year onwards. This resulted in an increase in the number of people who viewed our channel and interacted with our contents, as also indicated by the chart in Figure 5.28. This chart shows that the months with highest views were June 2021, October 2021, and March 2022, when we published: (i) the pitch sessions held during the TURNkey 2nd Consortium Meeting (June 2021), (ii) the presentations with which our partners took part in the ESC2021, and (iii) the video presenting the GeoSense cluster.

Besides the above, in Figure 5.29 we reported the proportion of views of our YouTube channel grouped by the following traffic sources:

- **External** indicates the traffic from websites and apps that embed our videos or link to our videos on YouTube.
- **YouTube search** indicates the search terms used by viewers on YouTube to find our content.
- **Playlist** is the traffic from any playlist that included our video (this can be our own playlist or another user's playlist).
- **Channel pages** is the traffic from our YouTube channel page, other YouTube channel pages, or topic channel pages.
- **Playlist page** is the traffic from any of our playlists.
- **Direct or unknown** is the traffic from direct URL entry, bookmarks, and unidentified apps.
- **Browse features** is the traffic from the homepage/home screen, the subscription feed, and other browsing features.
- **Suggested videos** are the views from suggestions appearing alongside or after other videos.
- **Notifications** are views from notifications and emails sent to subscribers.
- **Other YouTube features** is the traffic from within YouTube that doesn't fall into any other category, such as views from Partner promotions, or the dashboard.

Figure 5.29 shows that our page views were mainly due to posting our videos on external sources (e.g., Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn, and the TURNkey website) and searching for terms included in the content of our videos (e.g. the title, the description, and the hashtags). In the latter case, we found that the highest number of views resulted from searching on YouTube for *earthquake early warning*, *Strathclyde University*, and *earthquake Albania*. Finally, Figure 5.29 also proves that playlists with which we grouped our videos according to content and/or events played an important role in terms of views. In this regard, at the time of writing the deliverable, the most viewed playlist was the one with the ESC2021 presentations. Then, there are the playlists collecting the pitch sessions on EEW, OEF, and RRE, held during the TURNkey 2nd Consortium Meeting in June 2021.

Table 5.12: Statistics for videos on the TURNkey YouTube channel for the whole project lifetime.

	October 2019-April 2020	May 2020-April 2021	May 2021-Project End
Total number of subscribers	0	10	32
Total number of videos	0	2	43

Performance indicators; median (minimum, maximum)			
Views	-	215	25 (6, 214)
Watch time (hours)	-	4.1	9:37:09 (00:30:14, 01:36:55)
Average duration view	-	1:08	00:01:03 (00:00:06, 00:03:45)
Impressions	-	854	300 (36, 2692)
Reactions	-	5	0 (0,5)
Shares	-	26	1 (0, 26)
Engagement	-	31	1 (0, 31)
Engagement rate	-	3.65%	0.42% (0%, 11.11%)

Figure 5.28: Total views from the launch of the TURNkey channel to the end of the project.

Figure 5.29: Proportion of the TURNkey channel views grouped by traffic sources.

6 ASSESSMENT OF TOOLS TO PROJECT ACTIVITIES

The TURNkey Coordinator (NOR), with the cooperation of the WP7 Leader (EUC), periodically evaluated the performance of the dissemination and communication activities based on KPIs along with target values set in the project Grant Agreement. The used KPIs were not univocal but varied in relation to the adopted dissemination tools. The evaluation of the effectiveness of the dissemination and communication activities carried out in the three years of TURNkey is presented in Table 6.1.

Table 6.1: Dissemination and communication activities and corresponding KPIs referred to the three years of TURNkey.

Dissemination and communication activities and KPIs				KPIs	Achieved KPIs
Dissemination measure	Why	Whom	When		
1. Intranet/ 2. Share point (Google Drive) 3. Share point from UIce	Share internal material and information	Project consortium and EC	During project lifetime	Undefined	1. About 4.7 GB 2. About 25 GB 3. About 8.2 GB
Thematic workshop	exchange practice and opinion for the project progress	Project consortium	During project lifetime	Undefined	16
Internal meeting	Verify the project progress	Project consortium	During project lifetime	Undefined	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Monthly Project Coordinator + WP leaders' meetings <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Periodical meetings within each WP • Periodical meetings among all partners of the consortium
Project website	Disseminate project information, products and results	Everyone	During project lifetime	Undefined	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <u>New visits</u> 7591 • <u>Total visits</u> 13181.
Dissemination and communication material	Disseminate the project and its objectives	Everyone	During project lifetime	About 1,000 e-leaflets and e-brochures	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Project flyer sent to 136 newsletter subscribers and made available and downloadable on the project website and social media. The same flyer was distributed to the

					<p>Final TURNkey event.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Flyers on the TURNkey platform, OEF, EEW, RRE (in English and Spanish) distributed to the final TURNkey event. • 36 press releases • 2 radio interviews
E-newsletter	Disseminate project information, products and results	Scientific community and stakeholders	During project lifetime	About 200 every 4 months	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Newsletter 1 was sent to 125 subscribers • Newsletter 2 was sent to 128 subscribers • Newsletter 3 was sent to 136 subscribers. • Newsletter 4 was sent to 139 subscribers • Newsletter 5 was sent to 141 subscribers • Newsletter 6 was sent to 142 subscribers • Newsletter 7 was sent to 142 subscribers • Newsletter 8 was sent to 142 subscribers • Newsletter 9 was sent to 141 subscribers • Newsletter 10 was sent to 140 subscribers • Newsletter 11 was sent to 139 subscribers • Newsletter 12 was sent to 139 subscribers

Social media*	Disseminate project information, products and results	Everyone	During project lifetime	Undefined	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Facebook 131 followers 74 Posts • LinkedIn 215 followers 89 posts • Twitter 234 followers 89 Tweets • YouTube 32 subscribers 43 Video.
Publication of high-quality articles	Disseminate project activities and results	Scientific community	During project lifetime	≥25	35 (one of which in press) but more are expected.
Organisation of conferences, workshop, and similar events	Disseminate project activities and results	Scientific community, Stakeholders, and Policy makers	During project lifetime	Undefined	13
Participation to academic conferences, invited seminars and workshop	Disseminate project activities and results	Scientific community	During project lifetime	Undefined	14
Participation in activities organised jointly with other EU project(s)	Disseminate project activities and results	Scientific community, Stakeholders, and Policy makers	During project lifetime	Undefined	11
University teaching	Disseminate project activities and results	Scientific community	During project lifetime	Undefined	3
Final project conference	Present the project results, as well as involve and mobilize all relevant stakeholders	Scientific community and Stakeholders (e.g., EU decision makers, Governments, and Industry)	End of the project	About 100	About 70

*It is expected that some more posts (and videos) will be published on each TURNkey social media account.

7 CONCLUSION

This deliverable aims to report the effectiveness of the dissemination and communication activities undertaken during the three years of TURNkey (June 2019-May 2022) within WP7. The results of the adopted communication and dissemination strategy were continuously monitored to assess its effectiveness and progress and to formulate changes if necessary. The success of the dissemination strategy was assessed through a set of KPIs that were continuously monitored by the WP7 leader (EUC) and the project coordinator (NOR). The KPIs vary according to the channel used for dissemination/communication (e.g., the number of views of the project website, the number of followers on TURNkey social media accounts, and the number of attended workshops or similar events where the project was disseminated) and are reported in the section 6 of this document.

Due to the COVID-19 outbreak that occurred during the project course, we had to find alternative ways to disseminate the project results as effectively as possible. Nevertheless, we made good progress in several dissemination/communication actions, as this document demonstrates. Some examples are the various virtual workshops organised and/or attended by our partners and participation in online conferences. We also developed alternative and new ideas to improve the dissemination of TURNkey on our social media accounts (polls, pitch sessions, etc.) to reach a wider audience. We also made a great effort to reach out to local and regional authorities as well as EU funding agencies. This was also done within the HRB service, where we had the opportunity to collaborate with other EU-funded projects, with whom we shared the themes and goal of making Europe more seismically resilient.

Collaboration with other EU-funded projects also took place outside the HRB service and led to a number of activities (e.g., joint sessions at conferences) described in this document. With these collaborations, we were able to disseminate TURNkey activities and results to a wider scientific community and explore further possibilities for cooperation.

Finally, to make the dissemination as effective as possible, throughout the project EUC always interacted with all TURNkey partners to ensure that the project results were disseminated and translated into exploitable outputs.